

D2.3 - ADVANCEMENT OF SUSTAINABILITY ASSESSMENT KNOWLEDGE-FINAL

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ABSTRACT

The transition from linear fossil-based systems to circular and bio-based systems represents an opportunity and a suitable pathway for achieving several SDGs. Indeed, circular bio-based systems depict a great opportunity to reconcile sustainable long-term growth with environmental protection through the prudent use of renewable resources for industrial purposes. This needed transition is a complex process, which does not simply require innovative technologies from the supply-side, but also societal transformations based on a multi-actor process. The circular bio-based economy meta-sector may be a good candidate to put forward a new economic model, which requires transformative policies, purposeful innovation, access to finance, risk-taking capacity as well as new and sustainable business models and markets. However, a critical assessment of the environmental, social and economic impacts of the current linear fossil-based economy, as well as of the improvement potential associated with circular bio-based systems, is needed to underpin the identification of policy priorities. Bearing this in mind, SUSTRACK is a three-year project aimed at supporting policymakers in their efforts to develop sustainable pathways to replace fossil and carbon-intensive systems with sustainable circular and bio-based systems (at the EU and regional scale), contributing to achieving the European Green Deal's objectives. This will be done by identifying environmental, economic and social limits of a linear carbon-intensive and fossil-based economy; improving existing assessment methodologies; assessing the environmental, social and economic impacts of the EU's current linear fossil-based economy; comparing multiple transition scenarios focusing on the most carbon intensive sectors; identifying priorities according to scenarios analysed in the project and develop guidelines and policy recommendations.

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The goal of achieving a net-zero emissions European economy by 2050 demands a shift from linear, fossil-based systems to circular, bio-based systems. This transition is vital for meeting the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals and reconciling environmental protection with sustainable growth. However, the complexity of the transition relies on societal transformations, cutting-edge technologies, and multi-actor processes, requiring a new societal and economic framework and policy priorities that align with the European Green Deal. In this context, monitoring systems, modelling techniques and data are key tools to support policy making and facilitate a better understanding of the complexity, trade-offs, and potential pathways to achieve a sustainable transition to a circular bio-based economy.

This report presents the results of the work carried out in SUSTRACK T2.2, which builds upon other tasks already carried out in the project. First, D1.1 gave a comprehensive overview of the environmental, economic, social and cultural limitations of the linear, fossil-based economy. It also identified gaps in overcoming these barriers in terms of knowledge, practical implementation and opportunities, and mentioned requiring effective strategies and policies, and collaboration among policymakers, research institutes and public opinion leaders to promote sustainable developments.

Second, D1.2 identified and confirmed challenges, via a comprehensive stakeholder consultation, that impede progress towards a sustainable circular bio-based economy (CBBE), encompassing the barriers identified in D1.1. It highlighted cultural barriers (e.g. lack of communication regarding the advantages of bio-based products, consumer confusion, mistrust due to ambiguous sustainability claims), economic challenges (relatively high costs and risks involved in setting up circular bio-based systems), environmental issues (e.g. concerns on the limited availability of biomass, lack of knowledge and data for assessing environmental impacts of bio-based products), policy barriers (e.g. missing supportive and/or complex regulatory framework, conflicting policy goals), structural discrepancies (e.g. lack of harmonised waste collection systems and infrastructure, lack of established markets and value chains for by-products), and technology issues (e.g. immature technologies, insufficient capacities of end-of-life product treatments).

Third, D2.1 provided a review of existing knowledge for monitoring and evaluating the transition to circular bio-based systems. It identified major gaps across indicators and approaches generally used to monitor and evaluate the bioeconomy across the three major policy-level analyses: 1) micro level (products, processes, companies); 2) meso level (city/regions); and 3) macro level (world, Europe, countries). Limitations in data collection and data quality represent major obstacles for the assessment and monitoring of bioeconomy, especially within the environmental and social dimensions. Other methodological gaps call for a proper way to clearly differentiate between the bio-based share and the non-bio-based share “impacts”, as well as linking bioeconomy models across the meso- and/or macro-level, including the need for bio-based business models that clearly depict trade-offs with the three sustainability objectives.

Fourth, the policy brief in D5.1 highlighted current barriers in relation to the transition to a CBBE and which possible policy opportunities exist to tackle these barriers.

Building on aforementioned work, T2.2 focuses on the development of new indicators applicable for monitoring and evaluating the transition to circular bio-based systems, which were identified as gaps across the set of indicators that emerged in D2.1. That report provided a list of research gaps and recommendations to advance bioeconomy monitoring and evaluation at the different policy levels. Three of these research gaps have been selected for further exploration in Task 2.2:

- *Governance indicator(s)*: to give insight into how stakeholders work together in achieving common strategic goals of a city/local/regional area, like via cluster organisations, industrial/regional/ministerial corporations, existence of circular bio-based economy strategic plans.
- *Monetisation of externalities indicator(s)*: to distinguish between market price and inherent value for externalities, like costs of greenhouse gas emission. This must permit a fairer comparison between fossil-based and bio-based systems.
- *LCA-based indicator(s)*: to integrate key impact categories for the bioeconomy, like (in)direct land-use issues, biodiversity, deforestation, soil/water quality, and related carbon emissions.

Knowledge has been developed on how these research gaps could be tackled, taking into account issues like system boundaries, methodological approach and data needs. The newly gathered insights could benefit the monitoring and assessment framework that has been developed in T2.3. Also, the enhanced framework will be supportive of the case studies that are analysed in WP3 and the definition of policy recommendations in WP5.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

1. Introduction	12
1.1 Objective of the report.....	14
1.2 Structure of the report	15
2. Governance indicators	16
2.1 Overcoming barriers in assessing Governance indicators: Insights and Strategies	16
2.1.1 Description of the Gap	17
2.1.2 Barriers to assessing Governance indicators	19
2.1.3 Strategies to overcome the barriers in assessing Governance indicators.....	25
2.2 Methodology to overcome the gap	27
2.2.1 Desk Analysis and Policy Review.....	28
2.2.2 Stakeholder Mapping and Analysis.....	29
2.2.3 Stakeholder engagement	31
2.2.4 Development of governance indicators.....	31
2.3 Proposed Governance Indicators	31
2.4 Conclusions and Future Perspectives	37
3. Externality indicators	39
3.1 Origin of the externality concept	39
3.2 Policy relevance.....	40
3.3 Definition of externalities	40
3.4 Internalisation of externalities	42
3.4.1 General concept	42
3.4.2 Approaches and methods to calculate externalities.....	44
3.5 Incorporating externality indicators in SUSTRACK	45
3.5.1 Approach.....	45
3.5.2 External cost indicators applicable to case study activities.....	46
3.5.3 Using externalities.....	51

4. LCA-based impact indicators	53
4.1 State of the art	53
4.2 Policy relevance	55
4.3 Limitations of LCA methodology	56
4.4 Filling the Knowledge Gap	57
4.5 Integration in SUSTRACK	61
5. FINDINGS	63
5.1 Knowledge development on Governance indicators	63
5.2 Knowledge development on Externality indicators	64
5.3 Knowledge development on LCA-based indicators	65
References	66

LIST OF FIGURES

Figure 1. Overview of how the output of T2.1 relates to other tasks in the SUSTRACK project ..	14
Figure 2. Visualisation of the Circular Economy (Butterfly Diagram from Ellen MacArthur Foundation)	24
Figure 3. Conceptual approach to internalise externalities in SUSTRACK	45
Figure 4. LCA Methodology (Source: Own elaboration)	54
Figure 5. Usefulness of LCA adapted to soil indicators at different decision-making levels (Source: Self elaboration)	55
Figure 6. Bibliographic consultation (Source: Self elaboration)	58
Figure 7. Indicator Prioritisation Matrix (Source: Self elaboration).....	59
Figure 8. The next steps to address "the soil gap" (Source: self-elaboration).....	62

LIST OF TABLES

Table 1. Research gaps identified in T2.1 that may be of importance for case studies13

Table 2. Map of local key relevant stakeholders (Prato textile district, Italy).....30

Table 3. Development of Multi-Dimensional Governance Indicator: Aligning SUSTRACK and BioModel4Regions for an Integrated Monitoring Framework32

Table 4. Integrated Governance Indicators for Sectoral and Cross-Level Monitoring in CBBE34

Table 5. Economic activities addressed in the SUSTRACK case studies46

Table 6. Some indicators analysed in the SUSTRACK case studies, per economic activity46

Table 7. Estimated external costs due to chemical production in the EU27 (per euro product) ..48

Table 8. Estimated external costs due to steel production in the EU27 (per euro product)48

Table 9. Estimated external costs due to cement production in the EU27 (per euro product)....49

Table 10. Estimated external costs due to t-shirt production in Asia and the EU (euro/t-shirt)..50

Table 11. Factors which are considered of an agricultural process by LCA methodology57

Table 12. Selected indicators for inclusion in LCA methodologies.....60

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS	
Abbreviation/Acronym	Description
AHP	Analytical Hierarchy Process
ANP	Analytical Network Process
BPP	Biotic Production Potential
CBA	Cost-Benefit Analysis
CBBE	Circular Bio-Based Economy
CE	Circular Economy
CSR	Corporate Social Responsibility
EC	European Commission
EIA	Environmental Impact Assessment
EU	European Union
IOA	Input-Output Analysis
LCA	Life Cycle Assessment
M&E	Monitoring and Evaluation
SDGs	Sustainable Development Goals
SOC	Soil Organic Carbon
TEEB	The Economics of Ecosystems and Biodiversity
WP	Work package

1. INTRODUCTION

A key output of WP2 in the SUSTRACK project is the development of a Bioeconomy Assessment and Monitoring Framework populated with a set of meaningful indicators. This report presents the results of the work carried out in SUSTRACK T2.2, which builds on other tasks already carried out. First of all, D1.1 started with a comprehensive overview of the environmental, economic, social and cultural limitations of the linear, fossil-based economy. It also identified gaps in overcoming these barriers in terms of knowledge, practical implementation and opportunities, and mentioned requiring effective strategies and policies, and collaboration among policymakers, research institutes, and public opinion leaders to promote sustainable developments. Then, D1.2 identified and confirmed challenges, via a comprehensive stakeholder consultation, that impede progress towards a sustainable circular bio-based economy (CBBE), encompassing the barriers identified in D1.1. It highlighted cultural barriers (e.g. lack of communication regarding the advantages of bio-based products, consumer confusion, mistrust due to ambiguous sustainability claims), economic challenges (relatively high costs and risks involved in setting up circular bio-based systems), environmental issues (e.g. concerns on the limited availability of biomass, lack of knowledge and data for assessing environmental impacts of biobased produced), policy barriers (e.g. missing supportive and/or complex regulatory framework, conflicting policy goals), structural discrepancies (e.g. lack of harmonised waste collection systems and infrastructure, lack of established markets and value chains for by-products), and technology issues (e.g. immature technologies, insufficient capacities of end-of-life product treatments).

Building on the work conducted in WP1, D2.1 provided a review of existing knowledge for monitoring and evaluating the transition to circular biobased systems. It identified major gaps across indicators and approaches generally used to monitor and evaluate the bioeconomy across the three major policy-level analyses: 1) micro level (products, processes, companies); 2) meso level (city/regions), and 3) macro level (world, Europe, country). Key limitations refer to no regular data collection and data quality, which are key problems for bioeconomy monitoring, especially within the environmental and social dimensions. Other methodological gaps refer to proper ways to clearly differentiate the measurement of indicators between the production and use of the biomass and non-biomass-based economy, the bioeconomy modelling across the meso- and/or macro-level, and the need for bio-based business models that present trade-offs with the three sustainability objectives. Finally, the first policy brief, D5.1, has highlighted current barriers in relation to the transition to a CBBE and which policy opportunities there are to tackle these barriers.

As mentioned, D2.1 included a gap analysis of existing monitoring indicators and methodologies for assessing the environmental, social and economic impacts of the transition from the current linear fossil-based economy to a more circular bio-based economy (CBBE). It resulted in a long list of indicators associated with research areas of the CBBE, where key knowledge gaps were spotted in case indicators were not yet clearly defined and/or measurable. Important gaps and weaknesses emerged in the reviewed literature with regard to measuring the social, economic and environmental sustainability implications of the CBBE, as well as to associated data availability. Data availability on socioeconomic indicators appears in a somewhat more mature state than for environmental indicators because of regular reporting in statistics. Nevertheless, the data quality is a weak point, also for social and environmental indicators, as these are not regularly collected and monitored.

At the same time, T3.1 selected ten case studies from four sectors that face critical challenges within the current linear system, which are construction, textile, chemicals and plastics (D3.1). Next, T3.2 matched the specific research needs of the case studies to relevant indicators that

make sense to be quantified. Then, it was explored which indicators are immediately applicable and which ones require additional development first. The work of T2.1 served as the basis for this mapping process. In this way, findings of D3.2 are back-looped to WP2 on the one hand, while they, on the other hand, provide guidance and suggestions about which new indicators to add to the monitoring framework in T2.3. D3.2 provided a short list with eight research gaps (

Table 1) that may be focused on under the actions in T2.2.

Table 1. Research gaps identified in T2.1 that may be of importance for case studies

#	Description
1	Need for better addressing (pure) social aspects related to bioeconomy within the EU bioeconomy framework and the five Societal Objectives. Social issues that should be considered may include human health, rural communities' development, equality, inclusiveness etc.
2	Need for better tailoring of EU monitoring framework for local policy makers. This may include the proposal of sub-national monitoring frameworks taking stock of available data at these lower territorial levels.
3	Need for further standardisation of bioeconomy assessment at the regional-city level (including proposal for monitoring framework, indicators, and methods) to enable comparison among cities/regions.
4	Coverage of governance indicators to give insight into how stakeholders work together in achieving common strategic goals of a city/local/regional area. E.g. via cluster organisations, corporations across industries/regions/ministries; existence of circular bio-based economy strategic plans.
5	Monetisation of externality: a need for indicators that distinguish between market price and inherent value, e.g., by monetization of environmental externalities. This would permit a fairer comparison between fossil-based and bioeconomy-based systems, supporting decision-makers and investors.
6	Impacts on rural communities (at the very local scale) should be considered when evaluating bioeconomy projects as these are the stakeholder category most affected by changes in the bioeconomy value-chains. In this line, the inclusion of governance/collaboration aspects between industries/stakeholders is key.
7	LCA studies should integrate and improve key impact categories for the bioeconomy. These are direct and indirect land-use issues, biodiversity, deforestation, soil and water quality, and related carbon emissions.
8	LCA-based indicators should cover the whole life cycle and not be limited to factory gate boundaries. Above all within construction value-chain studies.

Source: Deliverable 3.2

D3.2 has selected three out of the eight research gaps for further exploration in T2.2 because of their expected relevance for the case study analysis in WP3. They refer to better coverage of governance, monetised externalities and LCA impact indicators, respectively.

1.1 Objective of the report

The objective of this report is to analyse and develop additional knowledge related to the monitoring and assessment of the environmental and socio-economic impacts of the transition from a linear to a sustainable CBBE.

Building on the lessons learned from T2.1 and the findings and feedback received from the INSPIRE conference, D2.3 reports on the further desk research to address three of the critical research gaps identified and develops knowledge and recommendations to fill those gaps. Firstly, this should contribute to a monitoring and assessment framework (T2.3) that is better equipped for case studies in WP3 in analysing multiple sustainability indicators. Secondly, the framework will become more useful in advising and recommending decision-makers on instruments that could boost the transition process towards circular business cases (Figure 1).

Due to their relevance for policymakers and investors, the following three research gaps (out of the eight identified in Table 1) have been selected for further exploration and development in T2.2:

- *Coverage of governance indicator(s)* to show how stakeholders work together in achieving common strategic goals of a city, local or regional area, like via cluster organisations, industrial/regional/ministerial corporations, circular bio-based economy strategic plans.
- *Coverage of monetisation indicators that valorise* environmental and social externalities associated with production and consumption activities, like greenhouse gases and health issues.
- *Coverage of key LCA-based indicators* for the bioeconomy, like (in)direct land-use issues, biodiversity, deforestation, soil and water quality, and carbon emissions.

Figure 1. Overview of how the output of T2.1 relates to other tasks in the SUSTRACK project

1.2 Structure of the report

The remainder of this report is structured into three main chapters. Chapter 2 reports on how the research gap on the coverage of governance indicators can be bridged. Chapter 3 explores how to close the research gap on monetisation of externalities. Chapter 4 describes how LCA-based indicators can better address impact categories for the bioeconomy. Each chapter will pay attention to the concept, policy relevance, indicators to monitor, method and data needs, and how the developed knowledge can be beneficial to SUSTRACK. Finally, Chapter 5 concludes the report with a set of key findings.

2. GOVERNANCE INDICATORS

The SUSTRACK project carried out in-depth studies on the environmental, economic, social and cultural limits of the linear economic model, as well as on the various barriers and potential improvements associated with a circular transition based on the bioeconomy while identifying gaps in overcoming these barriers in four specific sectors: plastics, textiles, construction and chemicals (D1.1, D1.2 and D1.3). These studies underlined the complexity of the transition and its underpinnings, including the new socio-economic framework, social transformations or even new policy priorities in line with the European Green Deal. Policies play a key role in shaping the relevant markets and promoting the adoption of sustainable practices. Their importance is evident in creating an environment that is conducive to innovation, ensuring cooperation between actors and promoting the adoption of circular solutions (Huttunen et al., 2014; Kershaw et al., 2020). The European Union's commitment to advancing the bioeconomy strategy further highlights the importance of policy in shaping the regulatory framework (Bell et al., 2018).

Facilitating the transition to a sustainable CBBE also requires up-to-date monitoring and evaluation frameworks and systems that can help policymakers work in this direction. Therefore, the SUSTRACK research included a review of existing knowledge on monitoring and evaluation (M&E) of this transition, with the aim of updating the state of the art in bioeconomy M&E and opening the field for future studies (D2.1). As a result of this analysis, a list of 20 gaps was identified in the literature for different topics and specific indicators, 8 of them (Table 1) have been considered relevant for case studies analysis. In this context, the fourth gap concerning the “*Coverage of Governance Indicators*” is analysed in this section. While environmental, social, and economic indicators evaluate the outcomes of the CBBE transition, governance indicators assess the conditions that enable or hinder this transformation. They are indeed crucial for assessing and monitoring the effectiveness of policies and progress in strategies for the CBBE transition, as also highlighted by other studies, such as the Substitution Share Indicator (SSI), which measures the replacement of fossil-based resources with bio-based alternatives, or indicators aligned with the SDGs and forestry governance frameworks to ensure policy coherence (Jander & Grundmann, 2019; Linser & Lier, 2020; Ngan et al., 2019; Kardung et al., 2021). Understanding if and how stakeholders are involved in decision-making processes to achieve common strategic goals at national, regional and local levels, with the aim of providing policy recommendations, is pivotal to better address this gap and even to overcome it.

Finally, integrating governance indicators into the analysis of transition is, therefore, useful to provide a comprehensive and informed picture of the governance dynamics that permeate this process. The conceptual definition of governance indicators outlines institutional cooperation, procedural transparency, regulatory consistency, and adaptive capacity. These indicators are intended to serve as a guide to direct efforts towards effective governance towards the goals of sustainability and circularity.

2.1 Overcoming barriers in assessing Governance indicators: Insights and Strategies

The transition to a CBBE across sectors such as plastics, chemicals, textiles, and construction requires a coherent and well-structured governance landscape. To better understand governance challenges and opportunities within each sector, a structured literature review was conducted to extract sector-specific governance indicators. This review covered academic publications, grey literature, EU project outputs, and relevant policy documents produced between 2015 and 2024.

The review identified governance-related indicators through a dual-lens approach. On the one hand, it assessed the presence of indicators that reflect governance conditions such as regulatory coherence, institutional arrangements, and stakeholder involvement. On the other hand, it evaluated how governance performance is linked to enabling conditions for sustainability transitions within the four sectors. These indicators were systematically coded and categorised based on governance barrier clusters previously identified in SUSTRACK D1.1 and D1.3, including policy coherence, institutional coordination, and participation mechanisms.

For example, in the textile sector, indicators were frequently linked to policy incentives and extended producer responsibility (EPR) schemes that support sustainable procurement and waste management coordination. In the construction sector, indicators emphasised regulatory alignment between national building codes and EU climate directives, as well as the establishment of cross-sectoral planning bodies. In the plastics and chemicals sectors, governance indicators predominantly focused on the presence of chemical safety regulations, transparency in labelling, inter-agency coordination on product standards, and enforcement mechanisms for circularity targets.

The review confirmed that governance indicators are not equally developed across sectors. While the chemical sector shows relatively mature regulatory frameworks, its connection to circularity and bio-based goals is still limited. Conversely, the textile sector demonstrates innovative pilot governance mechanisms at the regional level (e.g., in Tuscany), but lacks harmonisation at the national or EU scale. In all four sectors, stakeholder participation indicators remain underrepresented or insufficiently operationalised, particularly regarding mechanisms to include SMEs, civil society organisations, and regional actors.

This sectoral review serves as a foundational layer for constructing a more coherent and integrated set of governance indicators. The extracted sector-specific indicators will be cross-referenced with broader governance frameworks and used to inform both the indicator development process and the cross-sectoral harmonisation discussed in the next subsection.

2.1.1 Description of the Gap

Despite growing attention to the governance dimensions of sustainability transitions, the operationalisation of governance indicators remains limited, particularly in the context of CBBE strategies. While environmental, economic, and social indicators typically focus on outcomes and impacts, governance indicators are intended to measure enabling conditions, institutional arrangements, coordination capacity, and stakeholder participation mechanisms that shape the trajectory and effectiveness of policy implementation.

The gap identified in SUSTRACK's earlier work, particularly in D2.1 and D2.2, concerns the absence of structured indicators that can assess how governance processes either accelerate or hinder CBBE transitions. More specifically, the lack of indicators to track cross-sectoral coordination, vertical policy integration (from EU to regional/local levels), adaptive governance practices, and multi-actor involvement makes it difficult to evaluate how governance is performing as a systemic enabler.

This gap is particularly significant given that the transition to circular bio-based systems is not only technical but inherently institutional and political. It involves navigating complex arrangements across ministries, agencies, sectors, and regions. However, most existing governance assessments focus either on abstract institutional design or one-off policy evaluations, without offering measurable indicators that can be tracked over time or across different territorial scales.

Moreover, while case studies, such as the Prato case in the textile sector, have revealed the importance of regional and place-based governance ecosystems, these lessons remain underutilised in EU-wide monitoring frameworks. There is also weak alignment between governance assessments in national bioeconomy strategies and those embedded in broader sustainability reporting tools, such as those used by Eurostat or the Joint Research Centre. Addressing this gap requires identifying governance indicators that are not only theoretically grounded but also empirically verifiable, adaptable to different sectoral contexts, and relevant to monitoring frameworks at both macro and meso levels. These indicators should provide insights into how policies are formulated, how decisions are coordinated, who is included or excluded from the process, and how institutions adapt over time in response to feedback and crises.

The gap related to the coverage of governance indicators focuses in particular on how different stakeholders work together to achieve common strategic goals at different levels (national, regional or local). This gap, therefore, highlights the need to assess governance structures, mechanisms and initiatives that facilitate cooperation and coordination between different stakeholders to advance the goals of a CBBE.

This gap is characterised by a number of key aspects that needs to be addressed, such as cooperation between stakeholders (e.g. cluster organisations, industries, regions and ministries) to clarify the extent to which different stakeholders work together to achieve common goals, or again the level of commitment, communication and coordination of the different actors. In addition, it is necessary to understand the existence and effectiveness of different national, regional or local strategic plans to carry out a proper gap assessment. Indeed, an assessment of strategic frameworks and policies to promote circularity in the CBBE provides information on the governance landscape and helps to identify key areas for improvement. The structure of governance is also a key aspect. Indeed, assessing governance indicators aids in understanding the institutional arrangements, decision-making processes and policy frameworks that shape the bioeconomy ecosystem. This includes examining the roles and responsibilities of stakeholders, regulatory frameworks and mechanisms for stakeholder engagement. The assessment of governance indicators also provides information on the alignment of policies and strategies at different levels of governance to support the transition to a CBBE. This makes it possible to assess the coherence and consistency of policies in promoting sustainability and innovation in bio-based sectors. Thus, by addressing these governance gaps and incorporating specific governance indicators into monitoring and evaluation frameworks, stakeholders can gain a deeper understanding of these mechanisms and develop more effective decision-making strategies, greater involvement and targeted interventions to promote collaboration and drive the transition to sustainable and circular bio-based systems at national, local and regional levels.

The final list of governance barriers has already been identified through a multi-stakeholder consultation process involving surveys and interviews with experts in the field of the CBBE (D1.2). An initial list of barriers was derived from an extensive literature review carried out in T1.1. This analysis, which focused mainly on grey literature sources, allowed the categorisation of the barriers into six dimensions: cultural, economic, environmental, governance, structural and technical. In this first phase, a total of 193 barriers were identified across the value chain, with a significant number associated with material processing, product manufacturing, end-of-life management and the system as a whole. These barriers were identified with varying frequency in the literature reviewed, and to develop the list of barriers for the next stage, we considered all barriers that were identified in at least three different reports. In total, 51 out of 193 barriers met this criterion. These barriers were then presented to a group of experts during the co-creation workshop "Limits, barriers and solutions to boost the transition towards a circular bio-based economy" held during European Green Week. Stakeholders were invited to express their perspectives, engage in dialogue and prioritise the barriers in terms of importance. Further

barriers were identified during the focus group, and the resulting final list was divided into four critical sectors (textiles, plastics, chemicals and construction). After the co-creation workshop, the barriers were reviewed, and to ensure alignment with existing terminology in policy documents and grey literature, stakeholder-submitted barriers were syntactically harmonised. For instance, suggestions such as. In addition, overlapping barriers were merged, resulting in a reduced list of 67 barriers.

Following this first identification phase, twenty interviews were conducted with experts from the four sectors (chemicals, plastics, textiles, construction) as part of subtask T1.2.1. The interviews aimed to confirm the results of the co-creation workshop, to allocate the different stages of the value chain per cluster in each sector and to identify missing barriers not previously identified in T1.1 or the co-creation workshop. The resulting list of barriers was used for the second part of subtask T1.2.2. An online survey to complete the validation and prioritisation process and to produce a final list of 10 governance barriers was produced. Finally, we reached a final set of 31 barriers after the application of a cut-off criterion. As the following step, we applied multi-criteria decision-making strategies, i.e. Analytical Hierarchy Process and Analytical Network Process, to select the most important barriers across different sectors (D1.3). However, we used the full list of indicators before prioritisation for this report to keep our scope broader.

The following subchapters explore in more detail the barriers identified and some possible strategies for bridging the gap. By analysing these barriers and identifying targeted intervention strategies, we aim to provide decision-makers with a set of practical tools and guidance to address complex challenges and facilitate the transition towards CBBE. The importance of an integrated and collaborative approach, involving different levels of governance and a wide range of stakeholders to maximise the impact of the measures taken and accelerate the transition to a more sustainable and resilient economy, is emphasised. A detailed description of the approach taken to identify indicators to close this gap is also presented.

2.1.2 Barriers to assessing Governance indicators

To identify barriers applicable to different clusters and to classify them as major, moderate or minor barriers, an EU-wide survey of relevant stakeholders was conducted over six weeks. Fifty-five representatives from nine European countries took part, 38% of them from specific sectors involved in the project. At the end of the participatory process, which included workshops, interviews, and surveys, a list of 10 key governance barriers emerged, covering a wide range of challenges that need to be addressed to facilitate the transition to a CBBE. The comprehensive list of governance barriers was already provided in D1.1 and D1.2. In this report, we make more general conclusions on the barriers not only under the governance cluster but also extracting information across different clusters strictly influencing or influenced by governance barriers.

While recognising the regulatory complexities and political conflicts, it is important to remember that many current sustainable policies remain aspirational and non-binding in nature. This approach can significantly limit the real impact of key targets such as reducing greenhouse gas emissions, managing food waste and replacing fossil fuels with renewable alternatives. Research suggests that while ambitious goals such as those set out in the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) can guide policy, they often lack concrete impact due to unrealistic timelines and targets (Singh, 2019). A detailed analysis of more than 3,000 studies shows that the SDGs have mainly influenced debates rather than bringing about significant institutional or legislative changes (Biermann et al., 2022). This limited transformative capacity is partly attributed to failures in policy implementation resulting from conflicts between environmental and economic objectives, inadequate incentives and ineffective communication with stakeholders (Howes et al., 2017).

Furthermore, policies that focus on absolute or 'zero' targets may not be the most appropriate for achieving sustainability, as they fail to recognise the complexity of problems and solutions (Rauch & Newman, 2008). Specific studies show that sectors such as tourism and road passenger transport, with their emission growth trends, clearly demonstrate difficulties in achieving significant reduction targets through voluntary approaches (Scott et al., 2010; Figueroa & Kahn Ribeiro, 2013). Similarly, sustainable food waste management, while promising to promote CBBE, faces challenges related to product multifunctionality and resource trade-offs (Mak et al., 2019). These studies highlight the need for more stringent and mandatory policies to achieve significant environmental improvements. Here, we explore the barriers identified and propose concrete actions to address them, to create the conditions for a more resilient and inclusive CBBE.

In order to identify barriers applicable to different clusters and to classify them as major, moderate or minor barriers, an EU-wide survey of relevant stakeholders was conducted over a period of six weeks. Fifty-five representatives from nine European countries took part, 38% of them from specific sectors involved in the project. At the end of the participatory process, which included workshops, interviews and surveys, a list of 10 key governance barriers emerged, covering a wide range of challenges that need to be addressed in order to facilitate the transition to a CBBE. While recognising the regulatory complexities and political conflicts, it is important to remember that many current sustainable policies remain aspirational and non-binding in nature. This approach can significantly limit the real impact of key targets such as reducing greenhouse gas emissions, managing food waste and replacing fossil fuels with renewable alternatives. Research suggests that while ambitious goals such as those set out in the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) can guide policy, they often lack concrete impact due to unrealistic timelines and targets (Singh, 2019). A detailed analysis of more than 3,000 studies shows that the SDGs have mainly influenced debates rather than bringing about significant institutional or legislative changes (Biermann et al., 2022). This limited transformative capacity is partly attributed to failures in policy implementation resulting from conflicts between environmental and economic objectives, inadequate incentives and ineffective communication with stakeholders (Howes et al., 2017). Furthermore, policies that focus on absolute or 'zero' targets may not be the most appropriate for achieving sustainability, as they fail to recognise the complexity of problems and solutions (Rauch & Newman, 2008). Specific studies show that sectors such as tourism and road passenger transport, with their emission growth trends, clearly demonstrate difficulties in achieving significant reduction targets through voluntary approaches (Scott et al., 2010; Figueroa & Kahn Ribeiro, 2013). Similarly, sustainable food waste management, while promising to promote CBBE, faces challenges related to product multifunctionality and resource trade-offs (Mak et al., 2019). These studies highlight the need for more stringent and mandatory policies to achieve significant environmental improvements.

Here, we explore the barriers identified and propose concrete actions to address them, with the aim of creating the conditions for a more resilient and inclusive CBBE.

1. Regulatory complexities and lack of support for the transition at the government level

The transition to a CBBE in Europe is hampered by significant barriers related to regulatory complexity and lack of political support. The difficulty of navigating a fragmented regulatory landscape and the lack of binding targets are the main challenges (García-Quevedo et al., 2020; Garcés-Ayerbe et al., 2019). Complex and poorly coordinated regulations, together with high administrative costs, discourage firms, especially small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs), from adopting sustainable practices. Furthermore, the ineffectiveness of environmental policies is exacerbated by a lack of adequate political support and loosely binding targets (Angouria-Tsorochidou et al., 2021). Many of these policies remain aspirational and lack concrete obligations, reducing their effectiveness (Singh, 2019; Biermann et al., 2022). Implementation failures due to conflicts between environmental and economic objectives, inappropriate incentives and

ineffective communication further exacerbate the situation (Howes et al., 2017). To overcome these barriers, it is essential to simplify regulatory processes and create incentives that support the transition to CBBE. Regulatory reforms should reduce complexity and administrative costs, thereby facilitating the adoption of sustainable practices by SMEs (Försterling et al., 2023). In addition, it is crucial to transform aspirational targets into binding commitments and to adopt effective governance frameworks to reduce uncertainty and ensure equity among businesses (Gawel et al., 2018). Concrete incentives and stronger policies could significantly promote a smoother and more inclusive transition to a circular and bio-based economy.

2. Fragmented regulatory framework across European countries and at national/ regional level

The fragmented regulatory framework is a significant barrier to the transition to a CBBE. Environmental and sustainability policies vary widely between and within European countries, creating uncertainty and complexity for internationally operating companies (Kirchherr et al., 2018). Although the European Union has launched initiatives such as the European Green Deal, the Biodiversity Strategy and the Circular Economy Action Plan to improve regulatory coherence (Spani, 2020; Paleari, 2024), regulatory differences remain a significant barrier (Falcone & Imbert, 2019; Maitre-Ekern et al., 2020). Global competition further complicates these efforts, as countries with higher environmental standards fear that their companies will be disadvantaged compared to those from countries with less restrictive regulations, creating a kind of 'race to the bottom' in environmental standards (Clark, 1995). Countries with less stringent regulations may seek to maintain their competitive advantage through looser enforcement practices, thereby offsetting conditionality pressures from countries with stricter regulations (Knill et al., 2008). However, harmonising policies at the international level remains a complex challenge, as concerns about 'environmental dumping' and capital flight by multinational companies require considered policy solutions that balance competitiveness and sustainability (Ulph et al., 2001). An innovative approach proposed to overcome this fragmentation is 'nexus thinking', which considers the interconnections between climate change, biodiversity and the circular economy. The European Green Deal, designed as an integrated strategy, seeks to address these linkages, but some crucial areas, such as marine use and the impact of biomass on biodiversity, still need in-depth management (Paleari, 2024). To address regulatory fragmentation, it is crucial to adopt a systemic approach that integrates policies and promotes coherence between different levels of government. Creating common standards and certifications and strengthening international cooperation are key measures to reduce uncertainty and facilitate the implementation of sustainable practices (Gottinger et al., 2020). Understanding the links between climate change, biodiversity and the circular economy is crucial to designing effective measures and ensuring a smooth transition to a resilient and inclusive CBBE (Lange et al., 2021).

Beyond variations in legal definitions and standards, fragmentation also emerges from conflicting roles and overlapping mandates among public authorities (PAs) operating at different governance levels. In many contexts, the lack of clear vertical coordination between national ministries, regional agencies, and municipal departments leads to regulatory ambiguity and administrative inefficiencies. For example, one authority may be responsible for bio-based innovation promotion, while another retains jurisdiction over land-use permits or waste regulation, without mechanisms for systematic coordination. This misalignment often results in procedural delays, underutilisation of funding instruments, or contradictory policy incentives. Such institutional incoherence is especially detrimental in sectors that require integrated governance (e.g. construction or chemicals), where environmental, health, innovation, and industrial policies intersect. Therefore, addressing regulatory fragmentation must also include clarifying governance mandates, defining roles and responsibilities, and establishing formal coordination mechanisms across governance layers from local to national and regional. To reflect this complexity, SUSTRACK's governance indicators include specific measures related to inter-institutional coordination and cross-

departmental integration, ensuring that vertical and horizontal governance gaps are made visible in the monitoring process.

3. Competing political interests with fossil-based industries (big lobbies etc.)

The transition to a circular and bio-based economy (CBBE) is being hampered by political resistance from the fossil fuel industries. These influential and well-established industries see the CBBE as a threat to their economic interests and use their power to slow down change. This manifests itself through lobbying to maintain subsidies, spreading misinformation and lobbying to delay stricter environmental regulations (Kirchherr et al., 2018; Försterling et al., 2023). To overcome these barriers, it is important to develop policies that balance competing interests and facilitate a smooth transition. Policies should include incentives for renewable technologies, subsidies for sustainable businesses and regulations that favour circular business models (Gottinger et al., 2020; Bataille, 2020). It is also essential to engage all stakeholders in a constructive dialogue to ensure that the measures taken are fair and acceptable (Tan et al., 2022). It is equally important to address barriers along the entire value chain and to encourage collaboration between sectors. An integrated approach is needed, including policy packages to stimulate both demand and supply of sustainable solutions (Werning & Spinler, 2020). Only through these combined efforts will it be possible to facilitate the transition to a more resilient and inclusive CBBE.

4. Lack of alignment and consistency between different policies

The lack of alignment and consistency between policies is a barrier to the transition to a CBBE. This stems from inconsistent regulatory frameworks that create confusion and conflicts between regulations, preventing companies from effectively planning and investing in the transition to a circular model (Kelleher et al., 2019; Gottinger et al., 2020). Legislative gaps, the lack of mandatory requirements and government support, and the absence of circularity standards and criteria in public tenders hinder the adoption of circular economy practices (Kazancoglu et al., 2020; Rizos & Bryhn, 2022). To overcome these obstacles, it is crucial to adopt strategies that promote greater coordination between different levels of government and create a consistent and stable regulatory framework. This includes the implementation of coordinated policies and the creation of oversight mechanisms to identify and resolve regulatory conflicts (Tan et al., 2022). It is also crucial to promote transparency and trust in the market through information sharing, the adoption of international certifications, and the implementation of financial incentives and awareness campaigns (Milios, 2021; Rizos & Bryhn, 2022).

5. Lack of market-based policies (e.g. subsidies or higher CO2 prices) to stimulate the market

The lack of appropriate market policies hampered the transition to a CBBE. Without financial incentives, companies tend to favour cheaper solutions in the short term (Scarlat et al., 2015). Market policies, such as subsidies and carbon taxes, are essential to make sustainable technologies cost-effective (D'Amato et al., 2017). However, market dynamics that discourage innovation reinforce barriers to CBBE. The lack of appropriate policies not only discourages innovation, but also perpetuates linear patterns and hinders progress towards a circular bioeconomy (Donner & Vries, 2021). Issues such as price competitiveness and technological uncertainty create a vicious circle that limits the adoption of innovative practices (Salvador et al., 2022). Instruments such as landfill taxes can promote circularity, but recycling subsidies sometimes lead to less efficient practices (Roa & Rosendahl, 2022). Other policies, such as carbon-difference contracts, can help, but run the risk of distributing the costs of the transition unfairly (Vogl et al., 2020). Corporate social responsibility (CSR) is crucial for influencing consumer demand, although there is often a gap between positive attitudes and actual purchasing behaviour (Lombardo, 2011; Etilé & Teyssier, 2013). CSR can improve risk perception and information asymmetries (Carlos & Menck, 2014), and CSR ratings are positively correlated with local sales, especially in areas with high education and income (Wei & Xiao, 2022). Technologies such as carbon capture and storage require government

incentives to avoid investment inertia and optimise social investment (Golombek et al., 2023). To stimulate innovation and make the transition to a CBBE more effective, it is crucial to create markets for circular technologies and adopt fiscal policies for 'true pricing' (Rizos et al., 2018). CSR-oriented public policies, such as consumer education and labelling regulations, can promote responsible consumption and strengthen the governance needed for a sustainable CBBE (Etilé & Teyssier, 2013).

6. Limited long-term policy reliability

The lack of stability and consistency in policies over time creates uncertainty for long-term investment in the CBBE. Businesses need durable and predictable policies to justify the investments needed to adopt more sustainable practices. This uncertainty can have a significant impact on long-term investments, particularly in the context of the CBBE, which is a priority for the European Union (Rodrik, 1989; Bell et al., 2018). The biofuel supply chain, which is crucial for the CBBE, is also affected by uncertainty and concerns about sustainability (Awudu & Zhang, 2012). Defining clear and measurable objectives and implementing policy monitoring and evaluation mechanisms are important steps to overcome this barrier (Tan et al., 2022). Ensuring policy consistency over time is therefore essential to enable businesses to effectively plan and invest in the transition to a CBBE.

7. Lack of supportive policy framework for product-related inner circles of the circular system (recycling, reuse, repair, redistribute, remanufacture, and refurbish)

The lack of specific policies to promote circular practices may hinder the development of the necessary infrastructure and slow down the transition to a CBBE. In particular, decentralised bio-waste management is an area that needs attention (Angouria-Tsorochidou et al., 2021). The potential for circularity in bio-waste and co-products is considerable, but requires life-cycle analysis to identify the best options (Corrado & Sala, 2018). The use of waste, by-products and scraps as resources in the bioeconomy is in line with circular economy principles (Figure 2), but conflicts arise between industrial and environmental policies (Philp & Winickoff, 2018). It is crucial to implement fiscal and infrastructural incentives to promote separate collection, reuse and other circular practices. European initiatives, such as the Green Claims Directive, aim to improve transparency and accountability of companies in adopting circular practices, but more robust fiscal and infrastructural support is needed to ensure the success of these policies. Fiscal measures that reflect the real costs of waste management and promote the circular value of waste can facilitate the creation of circular value chains and increase consumer awareness of the circular use of waste (Morseletto, 2020). Furthermore, it is crucial to involve stakeholders and develop policies adapted to local contexts in order to overcome existing barriers. Only through an integrated approach, taking into account local specificities and promoting concrete actions, will it be possible to move towards a more circular and sustainable waste management.

8. Legislative limitations for applications of materials when classified as waste

Regulatory restrictions can act as a barrier to the reuse and recycling of materials that are considered waste, undermining the transition to a CBBE. Overly rigid regulations can limit the valorisation of spent materials and the adoption of more sustainable practices (Rizos et al., 2016; Mak et al., 2019). However, updating regulations and introducing supportive policies can help overcome such barriers (Rizos et al., 2016; Mak et al., 2019). For example, policies aimed at strengthening the focus on consumers' environmental preferences, market value chains and business cultures can be beneficial (Rizos et al., 2016). Furthermore, the implementation of circular economy practices can expand and diversify market outlets for bio-based products (Maina et al., 2017).

Figure 2. Visualisation of the Circular Economy (Butterfly Diagram from Ellen MacArthur Foundation)

9. Lack of clarity around policy targets and trajectories

Assessing progress in the circular bio-based economy can be complex without clear and measurable targets. This lack of guidance can influence business decisions and investments (Kardung et al., 2021). As noted above, many current sustainable policies remain aspirational and non-binding, significantly reducing their real-world impact. This limits the effectiveness of adopted measures and perpetuates the lack of tangible progress towards key goals such as reducing greenhouse gas emissions and managing food waste (Singh, 2019; Biermann et al., 2022; Howes et al., 2017). To address this, a comprehensive framework has been proposed that includes indicators to measure the extent and circularity of material and waste streams (Mayer et al., 2019). However, it is essential to ensure that these indicators take into account the environmental pressures associated with CBBE activities (Helander et al., 2019). At the micro level, a balanced approach integrating economic, environmental and social aspects is needed to comprehensively assess progress on CBBE, also to overcome the limitations of non-binding and aspirational targets. At the micro level, it is important to adopt a balanced approach that considers economic, environmental and social aspects to assess progress in the CBBE (Kristensen & Mosgaard, 2020).

10. Insufficiently ambitious targets and limited policy drivers

The transition to a CBBE is a challenge of great complexity and urgency, requiring radical changes in policies, technologies and societal behaviour (de Boer et al., 2023). To meet this challenge effectively, it is essential to implement robust support measures (Gottinger et al., 2020). One of the main obstacles is the predominantly aspirational nature of sustainability goals, which often

lack commitment and specificity, limiting their real impact (Singh, 2019; Biermann et al., 2022). Aspirational goals influence public debate more than concrete actions (Biermann et al., 2022), and the lack of bindingness and incentives weakens policy effectiveness (Howes et al., 2017). The transition to a CBBE requires more ambitious targets and more focused policies on circularity (Morseletto, 2020). It is crucial to implement policies that incentivise research, investment and public support, and to actively engage consumers through education and awareness campaigns (Milios, 2022). Educational institutions need to work with industry, consumers and governments to develop and disseminate knowledge on circularity (Serrano-Bedia & Pérez-Pérez, 2022). A comprehensive approach is needed to address challenges such as informal waste collectors and health risks of e-waste by improving understanding and promoting circular practices (Liu et al., 2023; Milios, 2022). It is crucial to set concrete and binding targets, such as increasing recycling rates and reducing carbon emissions, supported by economic incentives (Venkatramanan et al., 2021). Systemic policies that integrate research, investment and public support are essential to ensure effective CBBE (Marvik & Philp, 2020). Addressing the current challenges requires bold policies and concrete actions to overcome the limitations of aspirational targets and move towards a more resilient and inclusive CBBE.

These barriers collectively underscore the need for a governance indicator framework that is both flexible and sector-sensitive, but also structured enough to enable comparability, aggregation, and policy learning. The next subsection outlines strategies designed to address these challenges.

2.1.3 Strategies to overcome the barriers in assessing Governance indicators

Addressing the barriers to assessing governance in the context of CBBE requires a multi-dimensional strategy that combines methodological clarity, stakeholder co-design, cross-sectoral integration, and robust data alignment. Based on literature reviews, stakeholder feedback, and alignment efforts with the EU framework, several interlinked strategies are proposed.

Improved modelling techniques:

This includes increasing the use of new modelling techniques, such as system dynamics (SD) and agent-based modelling (ABM), to complement existing bioeconomy modelling efforts. This would enable consideration of the structural and systemic changes required to achieve a sustainable bioeconomy.

Incorporate governance indicators:

This strategy involves assessing stakeholder collaboration, strategic planning and governance structures at national, local or regional levels to fill the governance indicator gap. These metrics can be piloted within case study regions (e.g. Prato) and scaled through EU-level datasets like Eurostat governance modules or JRC observatories. It also includes assessing the effectiveness of governance mechanisms and initiatives in promoting stakeholder collaboration.

Develop a comprehensive economic sustainability assessment:

One of the strategies for overcoming barriers in assessing governance indicators is to develop a comprehensive, sustainable economic assessment. This involves the integration of externalities through monetisation to inform sustainability issues and contribute to the design of market-based policy instruments and decision-making processes (further details on the externalisation are provided in Section 3).

Fill data gaps:

Improve data collection processes, improve data quality and address attribution issues related to the measurement of indicators in the bioeconomy. This includes identifying gaps in environmental, social and economic sustainability indicators to ensure robust data availability.

Creating Tailored Indicators:

Develop tailor-made indicators for different levels of decision making (country, city/region, product) to test their applicability and consistency. Identify research gaps in indicators, data sources, methods and models to inform monitoring and evaluation frameworks.

Establish monitoring frameworks:

Create a knowledge map and operationalise an *ad-hoc* framework for monitoring and evaluating the transition to a CBBE. Develop a database of indicators for monitoring and evaluating the bioeconomy, which will be tested and further developed in conjunction with case study evaluations.

Promote public-private partnerships:

Work with relevant industries to overcome barriers related to political interests competing with fossil fuel-based industries and to develop policies focused on creating a more favourable market for the bioeconomy. A holistic approach for promoting public-private partnerships in the bioeconomy is essential, as highlighted by Vale (2017), and an integrated approach promoting them in the bioeconomy can be implemented through different strategies. Chabbi (2017) emphasises the need for creative collaboration models and new management tools to address environmental and innovation challenges. Maurrasse (2013) underscores the importance of combining public, private, and nongovernmental resources in strategic partnerships. Raising awareness and involvement of both sectors through dedicated events and workshops can foster mutual understanding of the opportunities and benefits of collaboration (Troisi, 2011). The implementation of financial incentives such as subsidies or tax breaks can encourage companies to engage in bio-economic projects with public entities (Laus, 2021). The creation of collaborative platforms can foster the sharing of resources and co-creation of projects, facilitating the formation of partnerships (Gallegati, 2020). Technical and advisory support can help companies and public bodies find suitable partners and define common objectives (Santuari, 2020).

By combining these strategies, SUSTRACK aims to develop a governance indicator framework that is context-sensitive, scalable, and integrable into future monitoring and policy evaluation systems.

However, there are several challenges that have been faced with respect to the development and operationalising governance indicators in the SUSTRACK Project, which lies not only in the complexity of the governance processes themselves but also in several practical, conceptual, and methodological barriers that hinder their integration into sustainability assessment frameworks. One key barrier is the lack of a shared definition of what constitutes governance in the context of a CBBE. Governance is often used as an umbrella term encompassing policy design, institutional arrangements, regulatory coherence, and stakeholder engagement. However, without an agreed-upon typology, attempts to develop indicators tend to produce fragmented, incomparable metrics. This ambiguity also affects the clarity of objectives for indicator development—whether they should assess accountability, inclusivity, transparency, adaptability, or coordination remains context-dependent and often unresolved.

Another significant barrier, as a limitation, is the disconnection between policy instruments and measurable governance outcomes. Many policies relevant to CBBE (such as EPR schemes, green public procurement, or regional innovation platforms) are evaluated in terms of their output efficiency or compliance rates rather than their broader governance function. As a result, data

collection systems often fail to capture how institutions interact, how decisions are negotiated across sectors or levels of government, and how citizens or marginalised stakeholders are included in transition planning.

From a data perspective, the limited availability of harmonised and up-to-date governance data across regions and sectors represents a third core barrier. While some EU datasets (e.g., Eurostat regional governance modules or OECD institutional indicators) offer partial coverage, they are not tailored to CBBE objectives or transition monitoring. Many regionally rooted governance processes, particularly in the textile and construction sectors, remain undocumented or lack digital reporting tools.

An additional barrier is related to the difficulty in capturing qualitative dimensions of governance, such as trust, coordination culture, or the quality of participation, using quantitative indicators. These aspects are often context-dependent, sensitive to institutional histories, and resistant to standardisation. The tension between methodological rigour and contextual sensitivity thus presents a trade-off that indicator designers must navigate carefully. Finally, stakeholder feedback collected during the co-creation workshops and semi-structured interviews confirmed that the fragmentation of responsibilities across institutions leads to siloed decision-making and unclear accountability structures, making it difficult to assign governance performance to specific actors. This is particularly evident in sectors like chemicals and plastics, where multiple regulatory bodies coexist with overlapping but poorly coordinated mandates.

2.2 Methodology to overcome the gap

This section outlines the methodology used to identify, contextualise, and operationalise governance indicators for the CBBE transition through interconnecting existing regulations, case study analysis, stakeholder network mapping, and qualitative interviews to translate governance gaps into measurable indicators.

To develop a robust and operational governance indicator framework for the CBBE, a multi-step methodology that combines conceptual alignment, empirical grounding, and stakeholder validation has been employed. This approach, adopted by SUSTRACK, was designed to ensure that governance indicators are both theoretically sound and practically implementable across the four key sectors—plastics, chemicals, construction, and textiles—and applicable to both regional and EU monitoring systems.

The methodology was structured around the following sequential components. The first step was conducting a literature and policy analysis. A systematic desk review was conducted to map governance challenges and indicator gaps across sector-specific and cross-sectoral literature. This included peer-reviewed academic publications, Horizon 2020/Europe project reports, national bioeconomy strategies, and EU legislative documents. Special attention was paid to how governance was framed and assessed in each sector and how institutional coordination, participation, and regulatory instruments were being monitored or evaluated. Additionally, existing governance frameworks—such as those from the BioModel4Regions project, the OECD, and the UN SDG — were examined to extract best practices and anchor SUSTRACK’s indicator development in international standards.

The second step was stakeholder mapping and power-interest assessment. Stakeholder identification was carried out for each case study, using a structured typology distinguishing between public authorities, private sector actors, intermediaries (e.g., chambers of commerce), and civil society organisations. A power-interest matrix was then developed to assess the relative influence and stakes of each actor in shaping bioeconomy-related governance at local and national levels. This helped define target groups for engagement, clarified institutional relationships, and

highlighted areas of exclusion or asymmetry in governance arrangements. Further details on the stakeholder mapping and power-interest matrix for each case study could be found in D3.3.

The third step was the network analysis of governance structures. For selected regions, a basic social network analysis (SNA) was conducted to identify institutional linkages and interaction patterns among key actors. This step provided insight into the density and distribution of governance networks, revealing both collaborative strengths (e.g., multi-stakeholder working groups) and fragmentation points (e.g., disconnected administrative bodies or weak cross-sector linkages).

The fourth step was stakeholder engagement and participatory validation. A series of semi-structured interviews, workshops, and co-creation sessions were organised with stakeholders across the four sectors. These participatory activities served three purposes: to validate barriers identified in the literature, to assess the relevance and feasibility of proposed governance indicators, and to identify missing dimensions from the perspective of those directly involved in or affected by governance processes. Feedback was incorporated into the indicator refinement process.

The fifth step was cross-referencing with the EU inter-regional framework. To ensure cross-project coherence and support interoperability, a crosswalk was conducted between governance dimensions and indicators proposed by SUSTRACK and those developed in the BioModel4Regions project. This comparative exercise helped refine the taxonomy of governance indicators, ensured alignment on key dimensions such as participation and policy coherence, and confirmed the complementarity of SUSTRACK's more empirically grounded metrics.

The sixth step was the selection criteria and filtering process. Proposed indicators were filtered and prioritised based on a set of criteria including: (i) measurability, (ii) data availability or ease of collection, (iii) relevance to identified governance barriers, (iv) alignment with sectoral needs and EU policy goals, and (v) potential for integration into the SUSTRACK Monitoring Tool. Indicators that met all five criteria were retained for further development and validation.

This methodological framework ensures that governance indicators in SUSTRACK are not merely conceptual constructs but grounded tools capable of capturing institutional dynamics, supporting decision-making, and informing long-term monitoring efforts across the EU and regional levels.

2.2.1 Desk Analysis and Policy Review

As the starting point, a desk analysis of scientific and grey literature was conducted to identify governance-related policy instruments at national, regional, and local levels. Using a policy coherence and alignment linkage, the analysis examined synergies, gaps, and potential contradictions among instruments that the results are provided in Supplementary Material A and B.

As mentioned above, the collection and analysis of documents considers all levels of governance. In particular, the specific context of the Prato textile district case study is analysed (examined in more detail under WP3). Therefore, Italian policies are considered at the macro (national) level, focusing increasingly on the specific context of Prato, through the meso (regional) and micro (local) levels. This effort is also useful to achieve the objectives of the parallel tasks (T3.3; T5.1).

The focus on identifying discrepancies and inconsistencies between existing policies helps to overcome the barriers of misalignment and lack of ambition and, at the same time, to boost the harmonisation of policies at the national, regional and local level, ensuring a coherent regulatory framework.

The first step in constructing SUSTRACK’s governance indicator framework was a comprehensive desk analysis, aimed at uncovering governance-related gaps, regulatory patterns, and institutional arrangements across both EU-wide and sector-specific policy landscapes. The objective was to identify how governance is currently addressed in bioeconomy-relevant documents and whether existing frameworks include elements that can be translated into measurable indicators. The review covered a curated selection of scientific publications, policy briefs, European Commission communications, national bioeconomy strategies, EU regulations, and outputs from Horizon 2020 and Horizon Europe projects. Priority was given to documents published between 2015 and 2024, to ensure alignment with recent developments such as the European Green Deal, the updated Bioeconomy Strategy (2018), the Circular Economy Action Plan (2020), and sectoral initiatives such as the Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability and the EU Strategy for Sustainable and Circular Textiles.

This analysis revealed that while governance is increasingly emphasised in strategic narratives, it remains weakly operationalised in monitoring practices. Most policy documents refer to governance in qualitative terms, such as the “need for integrated approaches” or “improved coordination”, but rarely propose mechanisms or metrics to assess such processes. Exceptions include recent efforts under the EU Monitoring Framework for the Circular Economy and certain national bioeconomy strategies (e.g., those of Finland, France, and Germany), which include rudimentary governance indicators such as the existence of inter-ministerial coordination bodies or dedicated implementation roadmaps. Sectorally, the analysis showed variation in governance attention. In the plastics and chemicals sectors, governance is often framed through the lens of regulatory compliance and risk management, with less emphasis on systemic coordination or inclusiveness. The construction and textile sectors, in contrast, reveal growing experimentation with participatory governance models, particularly at the regional level, though these are inconsistently documented and evaluated.

Overall, the desk analysis confirmed that governance dimensions are inconsistently embedded in policy texts and rarely linked to structured indicator systems. This reinforces the necessity of developing new indicators that both reflect sector-specific governance challenges and enable multi-level comparability. These findings informed the next steps in the methodological process, particularly the identification of relevant stakeholders and institutional actors through mapping and network analysis.

2.2.2 Stakeholder Mapping and Analysis

Following the desk analysis, stakeholder mapping was undertaken to identify and categorise the key actors involved in governance processes across the four sectors targeted by SUSTRACK: plastics, chemicals, textiles, and construction. Stakeholders were classified into five primary categories: (i) Public authorities (e.g., EU institutions, national ministries, regional governments, local municipalities); (ii) Private sector actors (e.g., companies, trade associations, industry clusters); (iii) Intermediary organizations (e.g., chambers of commerce, business innovation centers, public-private partnerships); (iv) Civil society and knowledge stakeholders (e.g., NGOs, research institutes, universities, advocacy networks) and (v) Consumers.

In parallel to the desk analysis, mapping and analysis of key stakeholders and nodes involved in policy processes related to the CBBE [e.g. consumers, producers, cluster organisations, NGOs, policymakers at ministerial level or above] are performed. Specifically, the main stakeholders related to the case study of the textile district of Prato are identified (Table 2).

In this way, an attempt is also made to identify (i) the main nodes of the collaborative networks to detect possible blockages due to diverging political or industrial interests, also (ii) if there are some areas where greater stakeholder involvement is needed to overcome political resistance and

promote greater collaboration. This process revealed both structurally central actors (e.g., municipalities, Chambers of Commerce) and marginalised actors whose inclusion could enhance policy coherence and legitimacy.

Within each case study, a stakeholder inventory was compiled using publicly available documents (e.g., project consortia, governance plans, EPR schemes, consultation reports) and refined through expert interviews and workshop discussions. In addition to identifying individual organizations or actors, their roles in decision-making processes, level of influence, and involvement in bioeconomy or circularity governance were assessed. A power-interest matrix was developed for each sectoral case study, plotting actors along two axes: Power (ability to influence governance structures, regulatory instruments, or funding mechanisms); and Interest (stake in promoting or resisting the transition to a CBBE).

The stakeholder analysis served not only as a diagnostic tool but also as a guide for targeted engagement in the next phase of the methodology—stakeholder interviews and participatory co-assessment of governance barriers and indicator relevance.

Table 2. Map of local key relevant stakeholders (Prato textile district, Italy)

Type	Affiliation
National Research Centre	Istituto per la BioEconomia (IBE-CNR)
Company	Rifò Srl (Company born through crowdfunding in 2017 from the need to change the current fashion industry and with a mission to have a positive impact on the environment and society.)
Company	Comistra srl (For over 100 years, giving a second life to rags and textile waste by transforming them mechanically into regenerated wool, new recycled yarns, and fabrics of the highest quality for haute couture)
Company	Manteco (Italian Premium Textiles and Circularity since 1943)
Company	Lanificio Becagli Srl (a family-owned industrial company, working for more than 65 years on the creation, production and distribution of innovative, sustainable and controlled fabrics for the fashion industry. Founded in Prato, it has become over the years one of the world's leading textile manufacturers and a symbol of Made in Italy textile excellence)
Company	Lanificio Paultex (In 2016 Lanificio Paultex obtained from the Prato Chamber of Commerce the Cardato Recycled certification on several families of fabrics, produced with yarn made from recycled material)
Local Public Authority	Municipality of Prato (Office for Prato Circular City Project)
Research & Development	Next Technology Tecnotessile (A public/private research organisation registered in the Register of Laboratories of the Ministry of University and Research (MUR), which works for the improvement of technological innovation and competitiveness of companies)
Public Authority	Chamber of Commerce Prato-Pistoia
NGO/Platform	Solo Moda Sostenibile

2.2.3 Stakeholder engagement

Once the full group of key stakeholders is identified, experts are engaged via email, and semi-structured interviews are organised to assess their perspectives and views on the policy barriers and recommendations identified during the desk analysis phase.

The semi-structured interviews are built into two parts. The first part explores the views of the different stakeholders on the identified policy recommendations to overcome the barriers, then the Interview results were cross-referenced with outcomes from co-creation workshops and MML events. In the second part, the case study of the textile district is analysed in more detail in order to obtain further information and insights (T3.3). The extent to which the perspectives and interests of the various key stakeholders are represented in the decision-making and research process is assessed. This is crucial to assess whether their inputs are taken into account in participatory decision-making and public consultations devoted to the development of bio-economy policies.

2.2.4 Development of governance indicators

The process of analysis started with desk research and continued with stakeholders' discussions and interviews, ending with the final list of specific governance indicators. In integrating them, a focus is put on addressing specific challenges related to the identified 10 barriers. Attention is also paid to monitoring and evaluation mechanisms that take into account the identified barriers and assess the effectiveness of policies in overcoming them. For example, assessing whether policies are able to reduce compliance costs or increase the ambition and effectiveness of policies.

2.3 Proposed Governance Indicators

The full list of governance indicators gathered from the literature is provided in Supplementary Material A, and then a refined version built upon stakeholders' views and validation of data gathered from the literature is presented in Supplementary Material B. At this stage, a partial scheme has been developed as a starting point to be further developed and finalised. Insights about how the final list of governance indicators can support the analysis of case studies in WP3 will then be presented and discussed once the list is fully completed. Indicators will cover different governance levels, from national to regional and local. Table 3 represents indeed the starting point for the final governance indicators list. The data shown are built starting from the consistency check previously conducted in T3.2 to identify the indicators in the Bioeconomy Monitoring and Assessment framework, taking the report published by ISTAT - the National Statistics Institute of Italy - in 2023 as the baseline for identifying new regional indicators in addition to the preliminary list of them.

In addition to that, to strengthen the methodological foundation and cross-project coherence of the governance indicator framework developed in SUSTRACK, a comparative mapping exercise was conducted between SUSTRACK's emerging governance indicators and those proposed under the Partners' Horizon project (e.g. BioModel4Regions, 2025). This crosswalk aimed to identify areas of alignment, divergence, and complementarity to build a more integrated and interoperable governance monitoring approach that can serve both regional and EU-level needs. It also provides a conceptual governance model structured around seven core dimensions: (1) Strategic Planning, (2) Stakeholder Engagement, (3) Institutional Capacity, (4) Monitoring & Evaluation, (5) Policy Integration, and (6) Innovation Support, and (7) Competitiveness & Jobs. These dimensions are grounded in the principles of multilevel governance and emphasise participatory, systemic, and adaptive approaches to managing bioeconomy transitions.

Table 3. Development of Multi-Dimensional Governance Indicator: Aligning SUSTRACK and BioModel4Regions for an Integrated Monitoring Framework

Dimension	Governance Indicator	Indicator Type	Origin/Framework
Strategic Planning	Existence of sector-specific circular bioeconomy strategies	Qualitative (Yes/No)	SUSTRACK + BioModels4Regions
Strategic Planning	Integration of bioeconomy aspects in regional/local development plans	Qualitative (Yes/No)	BioModels4Regions
Strategic Planning	Degree of alignment of national or regional circular bioeconomy strategies with the EU Green Deal and SDG targets	Qualitative (High/Med/Low)	SUSTRACK
Stakeholder Engagement	Mechanisms for inclusive stakeholder engagement in place	Qualitative (Yes/No)	Both
Stakeholder Engagement	Frequency of stakeholder consultation processes	Quantitative (times/year)	BioModels4Regions
Stakeholder Engagement	The number of stakeholder organisations (industry, civil society, academia) participating in policymaking	Quantitative (# organisations)	SUSTRACK
Institutional Capacity	Presence of dedicated circular bioeconomy governance bodies	Qualitative (Yes/No)	BioModels4Regions
Institutional Capacity	Availability of training programs for local officials on circular economy	Quantitative (programs/year)	SUSTRACK
Institutional Capacity	Technical staff capacity for sustainability planning	Quantitative (# staff)	BioModels4Regions
Monitoring & Evaluation	Existence of formal M&E frameworks for circular bioeconomy policies	Qualitative (Yes/No)	BioModels4Regions
Monitoring & Evaluation	Regularity of performance reporting to the public	Quantitative (times/year)	SUSTRACK
Monitoring & Evaluation	Existence of adaptive policy revision mechanisms	Qualitative (Yes/No)	SUSTRACK
Policy Integration	Existence of cross-departmental coordination mechanisms for circular bioeconomy policy	Qualitative (Yes/No + Notes on frequency)	Both
Policy Integration	Coherence between regional and national sustainability policies	Qualitative (High/Med/Low)	BioModels4Regions
Policy Integration	Policies addressing interconnections across sectors (e.g., water-energy-food-materials)	Qualitative (Yes/No)	SUSTRACK
Innovation Support	Availability of funding programs for circular innovation	Quantitative (€/year)	Both
Innovation Support	Number of public-private partnerships in circular economy R&D	Quantitative (# projects)	SUSTRACK
Innovation Support	Participation in EU-funded innovation programs	Quantitative (# projects)	BioModels4Regions
Competitiveness & Jobs	Number of green jobs created through circular economy initiatives	Quantitative (# jobs)	SUSTRACK
Competitiveness & Jobs	Existence of local strategies for skills development in bio-based sectors	Qualitative (Yes/No)	BioModels4Regions

Competitiveness & Jobs	Support schemes for SMEs and startups in the circular economy sectors	Qualitative (Yes/No)	SUSTRACK
Competitiveness & Jobs	Employment rate change in target sectors post-policy implementation	Quantitative (% change)	SUSTRACK
Competitiveness & Jobs	Measures in place to reskill workers transitioning from fossil-based sectors	Quantitative (#people trained)	SUSTRACK

SUSTRACK's governance work, while similarly grounded in systemic thinking, emerged more directly from sector-specific analyses (plastics, chemicals, textiles, construction) and stakeholder engagement across different governance scales. As such, SUSTRACK placed valuable emphasis on measurable institutional performance, policy coherence mechanisms, and practical coordination structures operating at national and regional levels, including in the socioeconomic dimension. As a result of this crosswalk, a refined list of governance indicators is being constructed to reflect both conceptual rigour and empirical measurability. Indicators that scored highly in both frameworks will be prioritised for integration into the SUSTRACK Monitoring Framework. The refined set will maintain compatibility with the inter-regional approach, enabling comparative analysis, mutual validation, and future interoperability between projects and EU observatories. This alignment not only reinforces the scientific robustness of SUSTRACK's governance framework but also strengthens its potential for scalability and integration into Horizon-wide assessment and reporting tools.

To ensure relevance and complementarity with international governance standards, SUSTRACK's dimensions have also been cross-compared with the 12 dimensions of good governance identified by the OECD (e.g., transparency, integrity, policy coherence, stakeholder participation, accountability, and capacity for implementation). While there is no one-to-one correspondence, several areas of convergence emerge: strategic planning, policy integration, and monitoring & evaluation directly align with OECD dimensions on policy coherence, evidence-informed decision-making, and whole-of-government coordination. Stakeholder engagement reflects the OECD's emphasis on citizen and stakeholder participation, while capacity building overlaps with OECD dimensions on institutional capacity, resilience, and risk governance. Innovation support and competitiveness & jobs, while not direct OECD categories, extend the governance framework to cover transformative economic enablers and outcomes relevant to transition management, particularly in sector-based systems like the bioeconomy (OECD, 2020).

This alignment allows SUSTRACK's governance framework to offer both continuity with established public governance standards and added specificity tailored to circular bio-based transition challenges. It also identifies a contribution by introducing dimensions (e.g., innovation support) that are less developed in OECD's generic governance assessments, thereby filling operational gaps and enabling context-specific policy learning.

Table 4 presents the final set of governance indicators developed through SUSTRACK's structured, stepwise and multi-layered methodology. It began with the identification of indicators through literature review and analysis of practical case studies across the plastics, chemicals, textiles, and construction sectors, capturing both policy-level and operational insights. This was followed by a comparative review of existing frameworks to integrate perspectives across different governance levels, from local to regional and national. The final set of indicators is designed by combining these multiple sources and perspectives, aiming to address the key governance barriers identified in the transition towards a CBBE. Each indicator has been categorised by type, governance

dimension, and sectoral applicability. Units of measurement and frequency, and proposed data sources, if available, are included to facilitate integration into the SUSTRACK Monitoring Tool.

By proposing a clear and coherent indicator table, SUSTRACK advances governance monitoring from a conceptual discourse to a structured and operational dimension. These indicators serve not only as tools for assessment but also as signals for institutional shaping more inclusive, coherent, and strategically aligned governance systems for the circular bioeconomy.

Table 4. Integrated Governance Indicators for Sectoral and Cross-Level Monitoring in CBBE

Governance Dimension	Indicator Name	Short Description	Unit	Frequency	Barrier(s) Addressed
Strategic Planning	Existence of sectoral circular bioeconomy strategy	Indicates whether a region/sector has an official strategy for circular bioeconomy development	Yes/No	Annual	Regulatory complexity, Strategic fragmentation
Strategic Planning	Degree of alignment with EU Green Deal & SDG targets	Assesses the strategic alignment of regional/national governance goals with EU Green Deal	High/Med/Low	Biennial	Misalignment with overarching EU targets
Strategic Planning	Integration of bioeconomy in regional/local development plans	Presence of bioeconomy objectives in local and regional development strategies	Yes/No	Annual	Strategic incoherence, weak localisation
Stakeholder Engagement	Stakeholder participation index in CBBE policy planning	Measures the extent and quality of stakeholder engagement in governance processes	Index	Biennial	Stakeholder exclusion, Power asymmetries
Stakeholder Engagement	Frequency of multi-actor governance consultations	Tracks the regularity of consultation processes involving diverse stakeholders	Events/year	Annual	Lack of transparency, Limited participation
Stakeholder Engagement	Inclusion of SMEs and CSOs in governance platforms	SMEs and CSOs are present in governance platforms	Yes/No + description	Annual	Marginalisation of non-state actors
Stakeholder Engagement	Mechanisms for inclusive stakeholder engagement	Existence of inclusive governance mechanisms involving stakeholders	Yes/No	Biennial	Governance exclusivity, procedural opacity
Stakeholder Engagement	Level of participation from industry, civil society, and academia	Percentage of participation from industry, academia, and civil society	% engaged	Biennial	Low inclusiveness, weak representation
Institutional Capacity	Availability of public funding for	Assesses funding allocation to support coordination,	% of CBBE budget	Annual	Under-resourced

	governance coordination	participation, and governance actions			governance, Funding gaps
Institutional Capacity	Training programs for local/regional governance officials	Counts training initiatives to enhance local/regional governance capacities	Programs/year	Annual	Capacity deficits, Uneven territorial implementation
Institutional Capacity	Presence of dedicated circular bioeconomy governance bodies	Formal presence of institutional structures dedicated to bioeconomy governance	Yes/No	Annual	Lack of formal governance structures
Institutional Capacity	Technical staff capacity for sustainability planning	Number of qualified staff working on circular/sustainability policies	# staff	Annual	Capacity gaps in governance institutions
Monitoring & Evaluation	Formal monitoring & evaluation (M&E) framework in place	Captures whether M&E mechanisms exist to track CBBE strategy implementation	Yes/No	Annual	Weak M&E culture, Policy opacity
Monitoring & Evaluation	Operational feedback mechanisms for policy revision	Evaluates presence and use of institutional learning or adaptive governance procedures	Yes/No	Annual	Static governance, Lack of institutional learning
Monitoring & Evaluation	Policy adaptability score based on evidence responsiveness	Composite score assessing if governance adjusts based on crises or stakeholder input	Score	Biennial	Inflexibility, Poor responsiveness to feedback
Monitoring & Evaluation	Existence of inter-regional governance benchmarking tools	Presence of tools to compare governance performance across regions or clusters	Yes/No	Biennial	Absence of benchmarking, Weak comparative evaluation
Monitoring & Evaluation	Regularity of performance reporting to the public	Frequency of performance reporting made public by authorities	Times/year	Annual	Transparency deficits, weak accountability
Monitoring & Evaluation	Existence of adaptive policy revision mechanisms	Existence of procedures for revising policies based on evidence and feedback	Yes/No	Annual	Static governance, weak feedback use
Policy Integration	Number of cross-sectoral governance coordination bodies	Counts formal institutions coordinating governance across ministries or value chain actors	Count	Annual	Institutional fragmentation, Overlapping mandates
Policy Integration	Level of policy coherence across governance levels	Assesses the degree to which policy objectives and rules	High/Med/Low	Biennial	Policy incoherence,

		are harmonized across levels			Regulatory inconsistency
Policy Integration	Level of inter-departmental coordination on sustainability issues	Extent of coordination between departments on sustainability topics	High/Med/Low	Biennial	Departmental silos, cross-ministerial disconnects
Policy Integration	Coherence between regional and national sustainability policies	Consistency between national and regional sustainability goals and policies	High/Med/Low	Biennial	Jurisdictional fragmentation
Policy Integration	Existence of nexus-based policy integration	Inclusion of multi-issue policies linking circularity, climate, and biodiversity	Yes/No	Annual	Isolated policies, lack of integration
Innovation Support	Presence of public-private partnerships in circular transition	Counts active collaborative governance projects between public and private actors	Projects/year	Annual	Lack of innovation support, Sectoral silos
Innovation Support	Availability of funding programs for circular innovation	Annual funding allocated to innovation in circular bioeconomy	Euro/year	Annual	Innovation financing gaps
Innovation Support	Number of public-private partnerships in circular economy R&D	Number of collaborative projects between public and private sectors in R&D	# projects	Annual	Weak public-private collaboration
Innovation Support	Participation in EU-funded innovation programs	Participation rates in Horizon, LIFE, or related EU innovation programs	# projects	Annual	Low access to EU innovation ecosystem
Competitiveness & Jobs	Number of green jobs created through circular economy initiatives	Total green jobs created as a result of CBBE policies	# jobs	Annual	Insufficient labour market measurement
Competitiveness & Jobs	Existence of local strategies for skills development in bio-based sectors	Local training strategies for building bioeconomy-related skills	Yes/No	Annual	Skills mismatch, education planning gaps
Competitiveness & Jobs	Support schemes for SMEs and startups in circular economy sectors	Financial and non-financial support for startups and SMEs in circular sectors	Yes/No	Annual	Startup marginalization, funding inaccessibility
Competitiveness & Jobs	Employment rate change in target sectors post-policy implementation	Observed change in employment rate post-CBBE intervention	% change	Annual	Lack of impact tracking on employment

Competitiveness & Jobs	Measures in place to train workers transitioning from fossil-based sectors	Training coverage for workers transitioning from fossil-based industries	# people trained	Annual	Insufficient transition planning
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2.4 Conclusions and Future Perspectives

Governance represents a critical yet frequently overlooked dimension in the transition towards a sustainable CBBE. Within the SUSTRACK project, we have addressed a significant shortcoming in existing monitoring frameworks: the absence of structured, sector-specific, and evidence-based governance indicators. Through the combination of a robust methodological approach, participatory engagement processes, and alignment with cross-project initiatives, we have designed a comprehensive set of indicators capable of capturing both formal governance structures and the practical functioning of institutions across different sectors and levels of governance.

These indicators are not merely technical instruments; they reflect the core values of transitional governance—transparency, inclusiveness, adaptability, and coordination—translated into measurable forms adapted to the complex realities of circular transitions across diverse industrial and territorial settings. Their development draws on both conceptual inputs, notably from frameworks of SUSTRACK and Partner’s Project such as BioModel4Regions, and the empirical evidence base generated through SUSTRACK’s literature reviews, stakeholder engagement activities, and case study analyses.

Looking ahead, the application of these governance indicators is foreseen across several strategic dimensions:

- **Integration into the SUSTRACK Monitoring Framework and Tool:** The integration of indicators into the SUSTRACK Monitoring Framework is guided by a pragmatic approach that prioritises data accessibility, consistency, and interoperability. While the governance conceptual indicator framework offers a broad menu of governance dimensions (e.g., coordination, transparency, accountability), their operational uptake will depend on the availability of reliable and regularly updated data at the EU and national levels.

In this respect, we fully acknowledge current limitations. Most of the existing governance indicators, such as inter-ministerial coordination or stakeholder participation mechanisms, lack harmonised datasets across EU Member States. The only exception is government support to agricultural R&D, which is also tracked within the Bioeconomy Monitoring Framework, and it offers a tangible entry point for integrating governance into quantitative dashboards.

- **Policy Feedback and Institutional Capacity Building:** By generating quantifiable insights into coordination mechanisms, policy coherence, and participatory practices, these indicators will support adaptive policymaking and inform adjustments to ongoing bioeconomy strategies.
- **Scalability and Integration:** The framework’s alignment with BioModel4Regions and broader EU governance models enhances its potential for upscaling and integrating across future Horizon Europe initiatives and regional observatories dedicated to monitoring bioeconomy transitions.

- **Dynamic Updating:** Given the evolving nature of governance shaped by institutional reforms, emerging crises, and new policy priorities, the indicators are required to be subject to periodic revision if the frequency of actual data is continuing. The responsibility for coordinating this dynamic updating process will lie with a dedicated observatory or a policy-support platform, to be proposed either as a follow-up EU initiative or through integration within an existing Horizon Europe cluster (e.g., under Cluster 6 policy interface structures or linked to Bioeconomy Monitoring Systems). In the short term, the SUSTRACK consortium suggests that regional innovation agencies, national bioeconomy coordinators, or European platforms such as the EC’s Knowledge Centre for Bioeconomy could serve as appropriate custodians for organising the continuity of data collection and indicator refinement. This iterative mechanism not only maintains the relevance of governance indicators but also fosters stakeholder re-engagement, institutional learning, and an evolving understanding of governance as a critical enabler of circular bio-based transitions.

In conclusion, governance should no longer be considered a background enabler but rather a central, measurable, and actionable component of sustainability transitions. The indicator framework developed through SUSTRACK offers a concrete and operational pathway to integrate governance into monitoring systems and decision-support tools, thus reinforcing its strategic role in shaping resilient and inclusive circular bio-based economies.

In addition to that, during the case studies conducted, several challenges such as interrupting production supply chains in the Prato district caused by floods were encountered in relation to the engagement of stakeholders with the risks posed by climate change on their performance. These challenges were directly linked to the concept of double materiality, which had not been fully integrated into the strategic outlook of some participants. Double materiality is regarded as a foundational concept in modern sustainability reporting, requiring that companies assess and disclose not only how environmental, social, and governance (ESG) issues are affecting their financial performance (financial materiality), but also how their operations are impacting society and the environment (impact materiality). Unlike traditional materiality, which is centred solely on business risks, double materiality is based on the understanding that enterprises are operating within, and contributing to, a broader ecological and social system.

This dual perspective is significant because it pushes companies to move beyond short-term profit goals and consider long-term sustainability risks and responsibilities. By adopting double materiality, organisations can identify where their value chains intersect with critical issues like climate change, labour rights, or biodiversity loss, enabling them to reduce negative impacts and align with global goals such as the EU Green Deal or the UN Sustainable Development Goals. Ultimately, it strengthens stakeholder trust, supports transparent decision-making, and fosters more resilient, forward-looking businesses.

3. EXTERNALITY INDICATORS

3.1 Origin of the externality concept

The prominent economist Marshall (1842-1924) made significant contributions to economic theory and also introduced the concept of external economies. His ideas were presented in his key work “Principles of Economics” published for the first time in 1890 (many editions). Marshall argued that economies could experience external economies, which are benefits that accrue to a firm or industry due to growth and activities of related industries or the overall economy. In other words, external economies arise from factors that are outside the control of individual firms or industries but have a positive impact on them indirectly. Marshall mentioned the following factors that drive economic externalities:

- *Similar business or industrial clusters* in close proximity can benefit from shared infrastructure, skilled labour pool, and exchange of ideas and information.
- *Knowledge spillovers* between firms in the same geographic area, as there is a greater likelihood of informal communication and diffusion of technological advancements.
- *Specialisation* of industries may attract skilled workers and suppliers, leading to lower costs and increased efficiency for all firms in that industry.
- *Infrastructure* on e.g. transport, communication and education, can enhance the productivity and competitiveness of all businesses in a given geographic area.
- *Positive feedback loop* as industries grow, external economies increase, attracting more business to the region, further reinforcing positive effects.

Marshall’s thoughts on external economies revolve around the idea that the location of firms or industries in proximity to each other could lead to shared benefits, creating a favourable environment for economic growth and efficiency. These concepts laid the groundwork for the later discussion in economic literature on agglomeration economies and regional development.

As a point of criticism, literature notices that Marshall introduced externalities to describe mainly the positive effects of industry scale and knowledge leading to better technology (Boudreaux and Meiners, 2019). Building on Marshall’s work, the British economist Arthur Pigou (1877-1959) expanded and refined the concept of externalities in his book “The Economics of Welfare,” published in 1920. He introduced some extended perspectives on externalities that relate to:

- *Definition of externalities*: broadened definition by also considering spillover effects of economic activities on *third parties*, which can be positive (external benefits) or negative (external costs).
- *Government intervention*: when externalities lead to market inefficiencies, corrective measures could improve overall welfare.
- *Taxation and subsidies*: these are policy tools to internalise externalities, like imposing taxes on negative externalities (e.g. to reduce pollution) and subsidies on positive externalities (e.g. to boost education).

In this context, Pigou introduced the so-called *compensation principle* as he argued that when external costs are imposed on third parties, those responsible should compensate for the harm caused. Opposite to Marshall, he was sceptical about the market’s ability to self-correct and highlighted that government action would be necessary to correct market imperfections through policies that internalise external costs and benefits.

In their book on environmental economics and natural resource economics, Tietenberg and Lewis (2023; various editions) also take into account a policy-oriented approach on externalities and how to use market-based instruments to internalise these. Stern (2006) studied the economics of climate change and emphasised the importance of internalising the external costs of greenhouse gases. Moreover, he provided policy recommendations for mitigating climate change. Baumol et al. (2012) discussed the economic theory of environmental policy and explored ways to capture externalities through market regulation. In the same direction, Field et al. (various editions) gave a clear introduction to environmental economics, covering topics such as externalities, market failure and the role of government to internalise external costs and benefits.

At least, it should be noted that the literature uses multiple synonyms for externalities, such as *external effects*, *spillover effects*, *indirect effects*, and *trade-offs*.

3.2 Policy relevance

Internalisation of externalities is regarded as relevant for creating more efficient and sustainable economic systems. Policies that support this issue can play an important role in addressing market failures and trade-offs and promoting the well-being of current and future generations. There is an appropriate set of policy instruments that can be assessed for specific types and contexts of an externality and stimulate the development of the CBBE, for example:

- *True costs or true benefits* incorporated in the decision-making of market participants can achieve a more efficient resource allocation and can better establish the overall well-being of society in their choices.
- *Economic incentives encouraging the adoption of cleaner technologies and sustainable practices* can improve environmental conservation, while reducing negative public health implications, and promoting the well-being of the population.
- *Designed policies* (e.g. taxes and subsidies; legislation and regulation) that account for the well-being of future generations can support long-term sustainability. Note that Pigou (1920) already identified such measures as appropriate ways to correct market inefficiencies and improve the overall welfare of society.

3.3 Definition of externalities

The traditional definition of externalities, as defined by Marshall and Pigou, refers to unintended spillover effects of economic activities on *third parties* that are not directly involved in the transaction. There can be positive (benefits) externalities and negative (costs) externalities. In the same context, there are various definitions of externalities used in literature, such as:

- TEEB (2018): “Externalities are the positive or negative consequences of an economic activity or transaction that affect other parties without this being reflected in the price of the goods or services transacted”.
- Perelet et al. (2014): “An externality arises when the actions of an individual, firm or community affect the welfare of other individuals, firms or communities. Externalities reflect the fact that social and private costs and benefits often do not coincide, so that an action which benefits an individual or firm may harm society in general”.
- Graves (2013): “An externality is defined as an uncompensated physical effect of a transaction between two parties on some third party”.

- Buchholz and Rübhelke (2019): “Externalities are the effects of an individual’s production or consumption activities on another party that are not compensated for through the price system”.
- Keohane and Olmstead (2016): “An externality results when the actions of one individual (or firm) have a direct, unintentional, and uncompensated effect on the well-being of other individuals or the profits of other firms”.
- Jonathan Gruber (2018): “Externalities arise whenever the actions of one party make another party worse or better off, yet the first party neither bears the costs nor receives the benefits of doing so”.

At the same time, the scope of externalities has been extended by addressing additional nuances and perspectives, like there are:

- *Economic externalities*: external costs or benefits that affect the allocation of resources inefficiently and don’t reflect the true costs or benefits of the market. In this case, economic externalities are regarded as a form of market failure.
- *Environmental externalities*: spillover effects of an activity on environmental conditions of a whole region or country, such as air, water and soil quality or land use change.
- *Social externalities*: spillover effects of an activity on the social conditions of a whole region or country, such as education, child labour or fair salaries.
- *Technological externalities*: technology advancements that lead to spillover effects to industries and societies beyond the innovator and create additional productivity and network effects (Duflo et al., 2013).
- *Behavioural externalities*: individual behaviour, considering psychological and social aspects, affect preferences, choices, and well-being of others (Luca and Bazerman, 2021). This definition goes beyond the traditional economic focus on production and consumption externalities.
- *Global externalities*: the action of one country can affect the entire planet, e.g. via environmental issues, like climate change. Addressing this type of externalities requires international cooperation (Yohe and Richard, 2011).
- *Institutional externalities*: legal and regulatory frameworks, property rights, and governance structures influence the way how externalities are internalised and managed (Schneider and Buehn, 2020).
- *Network externalities*: platforms can impact a product’s or service’s popularity based on its value. The more individuals use a particular product or service, the more valuable it may be for others (Suri and Jack, 2012).

The definitions of externalities have thus been evolving to recognise technological, behavioural, global, and institutional issues on top of the usual economic, environmental and social perspectives.

To summarise, the common elements in the used definitions are that an externality arises when the actions of a decision maker (e.g. producer, consumer, government) have an impact on a party external to the decision maker, which can be negative or positive. Further, the decision maker neither bears the costs of negative effects nor is compensated for the positive effects on the affected party or parties. As a consequence, the decision-maker will not take the indirect effects of activities into account when making the decision (Gruber, 2018). In case the indirect effects of an externality are taken into account, e.g. by an additional price factor to the market price of the activity that causes the externality, this is usually called *internalisation*. It ensures that costs or benefits of externalities are accounted for by those responsible for them, either through pricing

mechanisms, regulations, or other means. For designing market-based policy instruments, it can help to quantify external effects in monetary terms, which is called *monetisation*.

The concept of *internalisation of externalities*, e.g. via *true pricing*, is explained in the next section (Section 3.4). This study concentrates on the negative environmental externalities, i.e., the indirect negative consequences of an economic activity or a case study for the environment, beyond that activity/case study (Section 3.5). Though social externalities of an activity or case study are also of important recognition, measurement approaches are even less mature than those for environmental externalities. Therefore, social externalities still require more fundamental research, e.g. on the identification of suitable and measurable indicators, which is beyond the scope of this project.

3.4 Internalisation of externalities

3.4.1 General concept

In general, the research on sustainable value chains, industries or sectors focuses on specific aspects, such as *direct* economic costs and benefits, emissions, healthy food, or safe materials that they generate. Research hardly takes into consideration the *indirect* consequences on the economy, environment and society that arise via the interactions of those value chains, industries or sectors in the ecosystem. As addressed before, economic activities often cause externalities, e.g., the promotion of a specific value chain can bring financial benefits to a specific industry (*direct* effects), but at the same time can damage the living conditions of a whole region (*indirect* effects). Indirect effects are usually neglected because it is challenging for policymakers to internalise externalities due to difficulties in quantifying them. The phenomenon of accounting for externalities associated with economic activities is called '*internalisation of externalities*'. The positive note is that the issue is high on the political agenda, which has resulted in an increasing number of studies.

Externalities are thus regarded as spillover or indirect effects of activities that affect the well-being of third parties not directly involved in a specified transaction. In this context, a third *party* can be notified as:

- Person, group of persons, or a whole society.
- City, local or regional area, a whole country, the whole world.

The economic activity that causes the externality is diverse, e.g. in terms of *size of the activity* (e.g. a company, an industry, a group of industries or a whole sector), *type of value* (i.e. product and/or services related to the product functionality) that is produced by the activity (e.g. food, package material, clothes, plastics, furniture), *geographic area affected* by the externalities of the activity (e.g. city, region, country, world). Therefore, depending on the activity (size, value and geographic area), the associated externality can positively or negatively influence the well-being of the third party (a person, group, whole city or country):

- *Positive externalities* positively affect the well-being of the third party, e.g. via reduced air, water and soil pollution, better labour conditions.
- *Negative externalities* negatively affect the well-being of the third party, e.g. via increased air, water and soil pollution, more cancer cases.

The *internalisation of externalities* is a concept in economics that refers to the incorporation of external costs or external benefits associated with a particular economic activity into market prices. If externalities are kept outside the market price associated with an activity, they are

considered *external benefits* or *external costs* of the activity. Opposite, if externalities are incorporated in the market price, e.g. via subsidies or taxes, they are called the *internal benefits* or *internal costs* of the activity. In other words, the true costs and true benefits of an activity are then integrated into the market price¹.

The pricing of the externality, e.g. via paying a (carbon) tax, can be considered in the decision-making process of companies involved in that activity and in this way influence the indirect effects of the activity that go beyond its own scope. Different actors can apply different pricing instruments to internalise externalities, for example:

- *Industries* can reduce environmental externalities by investments in cleaner technology aimed at reducing air, water and soil pollution that improve the well-being of the region, or by investments in noise reduction technologies to limit noise pollution, which also benefits a broader group of people than its own.
- *Governments* can price environmental externalities, e.g. by imposing carbon taxes on the production process of a sector. This could result in lower carbon emissions, which improves the well-being of other individuals than the sector addressed.
- *Governments* can internalise social externalities of a specific industry, e.g. by requiring product certification about the use of labour or by subsidising specific education. This could indirectly reduce child labour in a region, improve lifestyle and health in general, etc.

In addition, calculation of internal benefits and internal costs can take place at different levels, such as along a value chain, within a company or industry, at the production or consumption side (Eidelwein et al, 2018). Saosee et al. (2022) give the following example of timber production in a specific region to clarify this:

- *Internal costs* are expenditures for investments, operational actions and raw materials that result from timber production (direct costs). The production process will cause environmental externalities via the emission of greenhouse gases and other pollutants. These will harm the environmental quality and human health and are paid by society, for instance, via medical expenses, accident compensation and taxes (EC, 2019). If these indirect negative impacts (or indirect costs) are given a price (e.g. via taxation) and added to the basic market price of timber, it means that *the externalities of timber production are internalised*.
- *Internal benefits* are the revenues obtained by selling wood products (direct benefits). If the timber production process contributes to the creation of local employment, these will benefit the social quality of the society. If these indirect positive impacts (or indirect benefits) are taken into account, given a price (e.g. via subsidies) and added to the basic market price of timber, it means that *externalities of the timber production are internalised*. An example of another positive externality regards the commitment of the public to sustainability issues.

As already addressed in Section 3.3, there are various instruments suited to address externalities and to diminish or eliminate the difference between (direct) market costs and (indirect) social costs via calculating a *true price* of a specific product, industry or sector, such as:

¹ This report regards the *true pricing concept* as a synonym of the internalisation of externalities concept.

- Taxes, subsidies, levies.
- Tradable permits, contracts, and liability.
- Legislation and regulation

3.4.2 Approaches and methods to calculate externalities

Eidelwein et al. (2018) propose three steps to identify environmental externalities, which could be accomplished with the identification of social externalities:

- *Step one:* design a diagram of the production process, identifying the processes/functional areas and material flows developed within the frontiers delimited for the evaluation.
- *Step two:* identify and record groups of environmental externalities (e.g. on pollution, greenhouse gas emissions and water consumption), and social externalities (e.g. on cultural aspects, health care, fair use of labour).
- *Step three:* identify the externalities at environmental and social impact levels.

Galgani et al. (2021) propose a *materiality assessment* to identify relevant externalities for the production process of a company or industry. Such assessment is often conducted as part of a sustainability reporting entailing the identification, prioritisation, and understanding of environmental, social, and governance (ESG) issues most significant to its business. Main goal is to determine which issues can potentially impact the organisation's ability to create value in the short to long run. Stakeholders, e.g. customers, employees or investors, and the broader society provide views on issues they regard as most relevant to the company or industry. This assessment helps organisations to prioritise efforts in addressing and managing ESG issues, to allocate resources effectively, and to communicate transparently with stakeholders about their sustainability performance. Herewith, organisations can enhance their sustainability strategies, better respond to stakeholder expectations, and contribute to long-term business success while addressing key environmental and societal challenges.

Now that externalities have been identified, they can be quantified or monetised. The valuation of externalities in monetary terms ensures that the (indirect) economic valuation of externalities can be compared across products, companies, industries, etc., and integrated in the decision-making process of private and public stakeholders. It facilitates the understanding process across decision makers on the urgency to compensate for the (negative or positive) consequences of a specific activity for the well-being of a third party, e.g. a whole region (Eidelwein et al., 2018).

There are various methods to value or monetize the externalities in question, of which the following are the most commonly adopted ones (Amadei et al., 2021):

- *Damage costs* are the estimated cost of all economic damage that results from negative externalities (Amadei et al., 2021). For example, emissions of particulate matter harm human health by causing respiratory problems; damage costs reflect the costs of these emissions to society.
- *Abatement (prevention) costs* is a proxy of the costs for preventing damage occurring to society (Amadei et al., 2021), e.g. the costs for preventing the emissions of greenhouse gas emissions. They indicate how much it is worth to society today to avoid the damage that is projected for the future.
- *Remediation costs* contain all the costs to be made to make a person as well off as he/she was before the breach of his/her rights (Galgani et al., 2021). The pricing of externalities is based on remediation costs that include a combination of costs for restoration, compensation and prevention.

Currently, there is no obvious consensus about which method to use to monetise externalities (Amadei et al., 2021). For instance, De Bruyn et al. (2018) and the True Cost Initiative (2022) use the abatement cost approach to monetise climate change, while Schneider-Marín and Lang (2020) apply the damage cost approach. Going into the advantages and disadvantages of the methods is beyond the scope of the SUSTRACK project. It is worth noting, though, that in project or policy appraisal, two versions of Cost Benefit Analysis (CBA) can be created: financial and economic. While the financial CBA is akin to project finance analysis, and only includes material cash-flow indicators, the economic analysis also considers the economic value of externalities that are not material. This allows to compare financial and economic performance, especially when using different methods for the economic valuation of externalities embedded in the latter (Green Climate Fund, n.d.; EIB, 2021)

3.5 Incorporating externality indicators in SUSTRACK

3.5.1 Approach

Figure 3 shows how SUSTRACK could account for external costs for the planet (right-hand side) and people (left-hand side) of an economic activity. In principle, this approach is applicable to the economic activities addressed in the SUSTRACK case study analyses in WP3, i.e. textile, construction, chemicals and plastics (Table 5).

Figure 3. Conceptual approach to internalise externalities in SUSTRACK

Table 5. Economic activities addressed in the SUSTRACK case studies

Economic activity	Case Studies
Construction	Cross-laminated timber; Biochar as an additive in concrete; Hemp insulation
Textile	Recycled carded wool from Prato, Italy; Man-made cellulosic fibres, like Lyocell; Latxa sheep wool from the Basque Country of Spain
Chemistry	Chemicals from waste; Bio-MEG, bio-MPG, and renewable functional fillers from wood
Plastics	Polylactic acid (PLA); Polypropylene from used cooking oil

Error! Not a valid bookmark self-reference. highlights some main indicators for which the case studies qualify (or quantify) the direct economic and environmental value of the respective economic activity addressed.

Table 6. Some indicators analysed in the SUSTRACK case studies, per economic activity

Economic activity	Indicators
Construction	Life cycle GHG emission; Forestry land use; Wood consumption; Intensity of fossil fuel use; Production of (biochar) concrete
Chemicals/PLA	Water use; Renewable electricity used for manufactured products; waste generated; % Biofuels produced with co-products, residues and waste; Land use; GHG emissions; Energy consumption
Textile	% Weight of textile waste in the total weight of total textile production

On top of the direct (*market*) effects of economic activity, its indirect (*external costs*) effects on the rest of the economy and society can be explored. The next section gives insight into some key external cost indicators that can value the indirect effects of specific industries on the planet and people. As noticed already, an in-depth quantitative analysis of valuing these external cost indicators (Figure 3, green box) for the overall (regional) society, as caused by case study activities (Table 5) is beyond the scope of Task 2.2. Instead, values of external cost indicators are gathered and illustrated via a quick scan analysis of existing studies (Section 3.5.2).

3.5.2 External cost indicators applicable to case study activities

An indicator is a measurement or value that gives an idea of what something is like, e.g. the production of an industry, or the greenhouse gas emissions of an industry and can provide decision-makers with information and insights in a systematic and objective manner. In this line, indicators can also be used to define and measure the indirect external costs of specific economic activities for the planet and people.

Examples of the main external environmental cost factors often addressed relate to (e.g. CE Delft, 2024; True Price, 2021):

- *Air pollution*: compensation costs of toxic emissions to air other than climate change (e.g. ozone layer depletion, acidification, photochemical oxidant formation).
- *Water pollution*: compensation costs of toxic emissions to water leading to ecotoxicity and human toxicity, and eutrophication of marine and freshwater.

- *Scarce water use*: restoration costs of using surface or groundwater (blue water) in such a way that the water is evaporated.
- *Contribution to climate change*: restoration and prevention costs of the rise of global mean temperature caused by increased greenhouse gas emissions due to anthropogenic activities.
- *Land use and biodiversity*: compensation costs of decreased availability of land for purposes other than current ones that displace ecosystem services, and restoration costs of land transformation and ecosystem restoration projects.
- *Material and fossil fuel depletion*: compensation costs of extracting non-renewable materials that express future loss of economic welfare to society due to increased scarcity.

Examples of the main external social cost factors often mentioned relate to (e.g. True Price, 2021):

- *Underpayment*: restoration costs for the wage gap between workers' wages and the local minimum wage to avoid future violations.
- *Forced labour*: restoration and compensation costs of reintegration, depending on the severity of the presence of forced labour in own operations and in the value chain.
- *Child labour*: restoration costs of missed education and compensation costs of future earnings losses due to the presence of child labour in own operations and in the value chain.
- *Health and safety issues*: restoration costs of medical issues and compensation costs for fatal and non-fatal incidents due to work in unsafe conditions.
- *Gender inequality*: restoration costs of the gender wage gap and compensation costs proportional to the female and male employees' gap along the value chain.

Dedicated calculations to valuing these external cost factors depend on the economic activity considered, such as where and how production takes place, the type of energy used and the intensity of the activity, its connection with other activities, and its dependence on other regions. In principle, each overarching external cost factor is the aggregate of multiple sub-factors that damage the planet and people, and which require costs to restore the damage caused. For example, the European Environmental Agency (2023) illustrates how complex it is to calculate the external costs of industrial air pollution at the EU member state level. The difficulty is also shown in a report of CE Delft (2024) that gives a detailed list of environmental prices for multiple emissions to soil, air and water. Values for external prices differ per study and case and must be regarded with caution: e.g. they rely on calculation methodology, assumptions taken, and production pathways addressed.

As noted, SUSTRACK did not specifically focus on calculating external environmental and social costs, e.g. for the case study activities addressed in Table 5. Instead, insights are obtained from recent studies that estimated the true costs of respectively chemical, steel, cement and textile industries in the EU.

The Greens/EPA group in the European parliament commissioned True Price (2021) to assess a true cost analysis of the cement, steel and chemical industries in the EU27 for the year 2019. European production of cement accounts for 61 thousand jobs (EU), the steel industry for 330 thousand jobs (EUROFER, 2020) and the chemical industry (including pharmaceutical, rubber and plastic industries) employs 3.3 million people (CEFIC, 2020). A detailed overview of the values of external cost factors is presented in Table 7 (chemicals), Table 8 (steel), Table 9 (cement), and Table 10 (textile).

Damage costs to people and the planet of the *chemical industry* amounted to around 169 bn€ in 2019, compared to its 603 bn€ turnover. The main shares of those external costs are attributed to

climate change, depletion of fossil fuels and air pollution. Average external costs - also mentioned the *true price gap* - of the chemical industry in EU member states were estimated at €2.52 per euro product.

Table 7. Estimated external costs due to chemical production in the EU27 (per euro product)

External cost indicator	External costs of chemical industry in EU (per € product)
Underpayment and gender discrimination (social costs)	€0.20
Air pollution (environmental costs)	€1.27
Water pollution and use of scarce water (environmental costs)	€0.05
Climate change (environmental costs)	€0.45
Depletion of fossil fuel and materials (environmental costs)	€0.65
<i>Total social and environmental costs ("true price gap")</i>	<i>€2.52 per euro product</i>

Source: True Price, 2021.

Damage costs to the planet and people of the EU27 *steel industry* amounted to circa 202 bn€ in 2019, compared to its direct turnover of 200 bn€. Herewith it is causing highest damage compared to the other two analysed industries. A large share of the external costs of the steel industry comes from air pollution, climate change, and depletion of fossil fuels. Average external costs - or true price gap - of this industry in EU member states were estimated at €2.01 per euro product.

Table 8. Estimated external costs due to steel production in the EU27 (per euro product)

External cost indicator	External costs of steel industry in EU (per € product)
Underpayment and gender discrimination (social costs)	€0.08
Air pollution (environmental costs)	€1.22
Water pollution and scarce water (environmental costs)	€0.05
Land occupation (environmental costs)	€0.12
Climate change (environmental costs)	€0.22
Depletion of fossil fuel and materials (environmental costs)	€0.32
<i>Total social and environmental costs ("true price gap")</i>	<i>€2.01 per euro product</i>

Source: True Price, 2021.

Damage costs of the EU27 *cement industry* to society amounted to circa 84 bn€ in 2019 compared to its direct turnover of 100 bn€. Main share of these external costs account to climate change and air pollution. Average external costs - or true price gap - of the cement industry in EU member states were estimated at €0.45 per euro product.

Table 9. Estimated external costs due to cement production in the EU27 (per euro product)

External cost indicator	External costs of chemical industry in EU (per € product)
Underpayment and gender discrimination (social costs)	€0.02
Air pollution (environmental costs)	€0.28
Climate change (environmental costs)	€0.42
Depletion of fossil fuel and materials (environmental costs)	€0.12
<i>Total social and environmental costs ("true price gap")</i>	<i>€0.84 per euro product</i>

Source: True Price, 2021.

The presented external cost values are estimates for the average EU member state. The study shows that external costs differ per country: in general, they are above average in Germany, Italy and France, and below average in the other member states. Further, the size and type of damages to the air, which cause the main external costs, differ per industry as such depending on the production process. In general, costs due to particulate matter formation are a key element in the conventional, fossil-based industries. When it comes to green - de-carbonized - production processes, estimates of external costs are limited (Energy Transition Commission, 2018).

Textile manufacturing is another key sector, both worldwide and in the EU. It provides the society with a diverse package of products, like clothing, shoes, carpets, furniture, etc. for homes, public buildings, work offices. The sector contributes significantly to EU27's economy in 2021 (EURATEX facts & key figures, 2022): it realised a turnover of 147 bn€, employed 1.3 million people working in 143 thousand companies, and produced 7.4 kg of textile per person. The other side of the coin is that textile production entails significant negative environmental, climate and social impacts as it uses resources, water, land and chemicals (EEA, 2024).

Textile consumption in the EU27 amounted to ca. 26 kg total textile/person in 2020, split into 11 kg industrial textile and 15 kg textile consumption (of which 6 kg clothing, 6.1 kg household textiles and 2.7 kg shoes). Compared to other consumption groups, textile consumption caused the 2nd highest pressure on water and land use, and the 5th highest on raw materials and greenhouse gas emissions in 2020 (EEA, 2024). As the majority of textile products are produced outside Europe, most of those pressures take place elsewhere: 85% of primary raw material use, 93% of land and water uses, and 76% of greenhouse gas emissions. The EU27 is an obvious net importer of textiles, accounting for 8.7 million tons of finished textile products with a turnover of 125 bn€, which means an import of ca 27.9 kg/person per year. At the same time, the EU annually

exports circa 11.2 kg/person to the world which are mostly used clothes. Cotton cultivation causes the main pressures on land and water.

The European Environment Agency (2024) estimated some environmental, climate and social damage factors caused by EU household consumption for clothing, footwear and household textiles in 2020:

- Resource use:
 - 175 million tons of primary raw materials (80% from outside EU); 391 kg/person.
- Water use:
 - 4,000 million m³ of blue water (88% from outside EU); 9 m³ of water/person.
 - 20,000 million m³ of green water (mostly from outside the EU; 1kg of cotton requires 10 m³ of water); 44 m³ of water/person.
- Land use:
 - 180 thousand km² land (mostly for cotton); 400m² per person (92% of land use outside EU)
- Greenhouse gas emissions:
 - 1 ton of textile production generates ca 15-35 tCO₂
 - 121 million tons CO_{2eq} from textile products consumed in EU; 270 kgCO_{2eq}/person in 2020 (75% is released outside EU).
- Chemicals (synthetic fibres, e.g. polyester, elastane):
 - Textile production uses 3500 substances, of which 750 are classified as hazardous for human health and 440 for the environment.
- Water pollution:
 - 20% of global water pollution is caused by dyeing and finishing textile products and causes health issues to workers and local communities.
- Social pressure:
 - Poor wage rates.
 - Poor working conditions and working environments in textile factories.

When it comes to estimating the external costs - e.g. in euros per kg textile product - of the damage effects for people and the planet associated with the textile industry, the type of textile goods produced matters. In 2021, the European Parliament (Greens/EFA) asked True Price (2021) to provide better insight into the social and environmental costs of the EU textile industry, in particular the dominant cotton t-shirt value chain. This value chain belongs to the clothing textile group and contributes one quarter to the 26 kg total textile consumption per person. The study has looked at the external costs of two cases: a cotton t-shirt produced in Asia and a cotton t-shirt produced in the EU. The main external cost factors are presented in Table 10.

Table 10. Estimated external costs due to t-shirt production in Asia and the EU (euro/t-shirt)

External cost indicator	External costs of a t-shirt produced in India, manufactured in Bangladesh and sold in the EU (€ per t-shirt)	External costs of a t-shirt produced in Greece, manufactured in Italy and sold in the EU (€ per t-shirt)
Forced labour (social cost)	€0.38 (in cotton cultivation) €8 (in fabric production)	€0.30 (in cotton cultivation) €0.23 (in fabric production)

Child labour (social cost)	€0.76 (in cotton cultivation) €1.25 (in fabric production)	
Underpayment, gender discrimination and negative health and safety issues (social costs)	€1.10 (in cotton cultivation) €0.45 (in fabric production) €0.45 (in manufacturing)	€0.14 (in cotton cultivation) €0.80 (in fabric production) €0.97 (in manufacturing)
Water pollution (environmental costs)	€0.36 (in cotton cultivation) €0.34 (in fabric production)	€0.36 (in cotton cultivation) €0.55 (in fabric production)
Air pollution (environmental costs)	€0.18 (in cotton cultivation)	€0.05 (in cotton cultivation)
Climate change (environmental costs)	€0.18 (in cotton cultivation)	€0.18 (in cotton cultivation)
Other damage (environmental costs)	€0.11 (in cotton cultivation) €0.07 (in manufacturing)	€0.11 (in cotton cultivation) €0.05 (in manufacturing)
<i>Total social and environmental costs ("true price gap")</i>	<i>€18.27 per t-shirt</i>	<i>€5.58 per t-shirt</i>

Source: True Price, 2021.

If the true price gap is added to the economic purchasing price of a t-shirt (not given in the study, as it may depend on size and weight), it gives the true price of the product (euro/t-shirt). Numbers show that the true price of a t-shirt also depends on the region where the t-shirt is produced, i.e. €18.27 per t-shirt if produced in Asia and €5.58 per t-shirt if produced in the EU.

In another study, the Impact Institute (2019) estimated the total social and environmental external costs (the true price gap) of a pair of jeans purchased in the Netherlands at 30 euros. In the cotton cultivation stage, external costs amount to ca 8 euros per jeans (50% due to scarce water usage and 50% due to water pollution. External costs in the fabric manufacturing stage account for ca 20 euros per jeans (15 euros social costs due to forced labour, child labour and underpayment across the value chain in India). Finally, the manufacturing stage leads to another social external cost of 3 euros per jeans.

3.5.3 Using externalities

The information in the tables in Section 3.5.2 highlights hotspots for intervention that were to mitigate external costs that go along with industrial production, which is of high policy relevance. Such interventions could, e.g. deal with the adoption of circular and green construction pathways via the promotion of recycling and reuse of materials like textiles and plastics. For example, promoting recycling and reuse of textiles could reduce external costs by 20-30% according to the Ellen MacArthur Foundation (2017). Further, sustainable practices to lower pollution costs can be stimulated by using low-carbon construction materials and technologies to reduce GHG emissions, implementing stricter wastewater treatment standards and reducing microplastics can

significantly lower pollution costs. Also, encouraging organic cotton farming and sustainable materials use can mitigate soil degradation and biodiversity loss.

The calculation of external costs of economic activities is a complex task, as it depends on type of industry, the production process line considered, the connection of the industry with other activities in the value chain, the geographical location where production takes place and its reliance on other regions for materials, land and labour.

Nevertheless, the examples of external costs calculations in the previous section give a relevant overview of the types and size of damages brought to the planet and people due to the activities of chemical, steel, cement and textile industries in the EU. As noticed before, these are not ‘the’ values, as the quantification has been conducted for a specific product or product line, as well as the production process applied.

In that sense, the external cost indicators for damage factors discussed in Section 3.5.2 are useful references to other tasks in SUSTRACK, but above all are useful indicators for monitoring the development of the circular bioeconomy in general (beyond SUSTRACK). They can enhance the monitoring and assessment framework developed in T2.3 and equip it even better for analysing multiple sustainability indicators and advising decision-makers on instruments that could stimulate the transition process towards circular business cases (Figure 1). Due to the complex and time-intensive nature of the activity, measuring external cost indicators cannot be applied in the case study activities addressed in WP3.

On the other hand, the type of indicators explored in Section 3.5.2 can provide some insights into the size of external costs that result from specific industrial production. In this respect, the PLA case study in SUSTRACK recognises land and water as the main resources at risk of depletion from bioplastics, though so far only a tiny fraction of agricultural land is used for biobased products purposes because current biobased plastic production is still small (ca 2% in total plastic production). Microplastics pollution is another potential external cost identified: for PLA, despite being biodegradable in contrast to PP from UCO, the microplastics are not persistent and still get released into the environment. Further, PLA production requires irrigation water for crop growing; however, for the two water-based production steps (dextrose and lactic acid production), much less water compared to other conventional plastics like polyamide and cellophane is required. Lastly, the PLA case study mentions possible policy interventions to internalise external costs, which are bans on certain (conventional plastic) products, producer tax for each ton of fossil-based plastic, eco-design requirements, standards of recycling, waste collection targets and green procurements.

Raising awareness of the existence of external costs that go along with the reparation of social and environmental damages caused by economic activity is a pertinent reason for addressing them in the monitoring framework. The identified external cost indicators could, anyway, improve decision making about which value chain or industry to support in a specific region, i.e. to support a circular business case or to continue with business-as-usual linear production processes.

4. LCA-BASED IMPACT INDICATORS

4.1 State of the art

In recent years, soil health has become a growing concern across the European Union, with more than 60% of soils classified as unhealthy due to processes such as erosion, compaction, loss of organic matter, salinisation, and contamination (EC, 2021). These processes undermine the capacity of soils to provide essential ecosystem services, including biomass production, carbon storage, water filtration, and biodiversity conservation. As a response, the EU has launched initiatives such as the “Soil Strategy for 2030 and the Mission: A Soil Deal for Europe under Horizon Europe”, which aim to protect and restore European soils.

Soil is both a natural resource and a productive asset critical to the success of the circular bioeconomy. Sectors like agriculture, livestock, forestry, and biorefineries rely directly on healthy soil. In turn, bio-based outputs such as compost, digestate, and biochar can improve soil quality, particularly its organic matter content (Andrade Díaz et al., 2024). Despite this bidirectional interaction, soil health remains insufficiently represented in mainstream sustainability assessment tools.

Among these tools, Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) is one of the most widespread methodologies used to evaluate the environmental performance of products, processes, and services. LCA has evolved over several decades, with its current structure formalised in the ISO 14040 and ISO 14044 standards (ISO, 2006), and it is widely applied in circular economy and bioeconomy studies (Bastianoni et al., 2023). The method systematically accounts for inputs, outputs and emissions across the life cycle of a product, from raw material extraction to end-of-life.

However, traditional LCA methodologies do not adequately assess soil quality or degradation. Most LCA models treat soil as a passive medium, analysing what goes in (e.g., fertilisers) and out (e.g., emissions), but not how the process affects the soil’s internal state (Galdric, 2014). For example, critical impacts such as erosion, biodiversity loss, or depletion of soil organic matter are not captured, limiting the tool’s comprehensiveness in biobased systems (Hobson & Lynch, 2018).

This methodological gap is especially relevant for SUSTRACK, a project that aims to support the transition from fossil-based to circular bio-based systems. The project’s ambition includes identifying systemic barriers and improving assessment tools to enable sustainable policy development. Within this context, integrating soil quality indicators into LCA represents a key opportunity to enhance the robustness and relevance of LCA for bioeconomy transition pathways.

Figure 4. LCA Methodology (Source: Own elaboration)

Beyond traditional impact categories such as global warming potential or eutrophication, LCA must evolve to address categories particularly relevant to the bioeconomy. These include:

- Soil quality and degradation
- Biodiversity
- Land use and land-use change
- Carbon sequestration in soils
- Water quality linked to soil retention and filtration

However, capturing these aspects within the LCA framework presents several methodological challenges. One of the main limitations is the lack of standardised models to quantify soil-related impacts, which complicates the comparison and replication of results. Additionally, soils are inherently variable in both space and time, making it difficult to generalise outcomes across regions or systems. The availability of reliable data is another key barrier, as collecting site-specific soil information can be both time-consuming and costly. Finally, current LCA methodologies still provide limited integration of soil-related ecosystem services, such as nutrient cycling, biodiversity support, and water regulation, further reducing the comprehensiveness of soil impact assessments.

This section contributes to the SUSTRACK project's overarching goal of supporting the transition toward a sustainable bioeconomy by identifying critical gaps in current LCA methodologies, particularly regarding soil assessment. By clarifying the limitations and emerging needs related to soil quality integration in LCA, it lays the foundation for the selection of practical and harmonised

indicators that will enhance the environmental robustness of life cycle-based decision-making tools in the bioeconomy context.

4.2 Policy relevance

In the context of accelerating the transition towards sustainability, one of the main challenges faced by governments and institutions is the design of policies that are aligned with the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) and the European Green Deal. Tools such as LCA are increasingly recognised for their ability to inform evidence-based decision-making by providing scientifically robust data on the environmental impacts of products, processes, and systems (Hobson & Lynch, 2018).

By offering a systemic perspective that encompasses the entire life cycle of a product, from raw material extraction to end of life, LCA enables policymakers to identify environmental hotspots, evaluate trade-offs, and compare alternative scenarios. This supports the development of more coherent, cost-effective and environmentally sound strategies at multiple governance levels (micro, meso, macro) (Jeswani et al., 2010).

Figure 5. Usefulness of LCA adapted to soil indicators at different decision-making levels (Source: Self elaboration)

However, traditional LCA methods have certain limitations that can reduce their policy relevance. Key social and economic impacts are often excluded, and the methodology may oversimplify complex environmental interactions, particularly those related to soil health, biodiversity, or ecosystem services. To address these limitations, LCA can be combined with complementary tools such as Cost-Benefit Analysis (CBA), Environmental Impact Assessment (EIA), or Input-Output Analysis (IOA), thus enabling a more integrated and multidimensional sustainability assessment.

The integration of soil quality indicators into LCA is particularly relevant from a policy perspective. It would allow for the evaluation of long-term soil degradation risks, carbon sequestration

potential, and the impacts of agricultural and bio-based practices on land productivity. Such insights are crucial for the design of policies related to agriculture, land use planning, climate change mitigation, and circular bioeconomy strategies.

Furthermore, improving LCA by incorporating soil-related dimensions could also enhance its utility for companies, public administrations, and consumers, enabling more informed decisions, responsible supply chain management, and sustainable innovation. As such, the methodological improvements proposed in SUSTRACK have the potential to contribute not only to better assessments but also to more effective and forward-looking policy instruments at national and European levels (Talwar & Holden, 2022).

4.3 Limitations of LCA methodology

Although LCA has evolved significantly in recent decades and is now widely used in environmental evaluation, it still presents notable limitations, especially when applied to the complex dynamics of the bioeconomy.

One of the main challenges relates to the intensive data collection process, which can be time-consuming and costly. This often leads to reliance on secondary or estimated data, which reduces the robustness and precision of the results (Talwar & Holden, 2022). In many cases, the goal and scope definition, essential for framing the system boundaries, can be either unclear or too narrow, omitting key life cycle stages such as raw material extraction or end-of-life disposal.

A further limitation is the lack of harmonisation and standardisation in the methodology. This variability among LCA studies hampers comparability and reproducibility, especially across different sectors and geographies. In the context of the circular bioeconomy, additional gaps have been identified: for example, the omission of industrial symbiosis, the undervaluation of transformative system changes, and limited applicability to emerging technologies.

When it comes to assessing soil impacts, the limitations become even more evident. While LCA quantifies inputs and outputs (e.g. fertiliser use, GHG emissions), it generally fails to capture the internal physical, chemical, and biological processes that occur in soil. These include changes in organic matter, microbial activity, compaction, erosion, salinity, and biodiversity, all of which influence the productivity and sustainability of bio-based systems (Hobson & Lynch, 2018).

Moreover, soil is a dynamic and living system, highly influenced by local environmental conditions such as climate, topography, soil type, and management practices. This complexity complicates the development of generalisable models. Additionally, most LCA tools evaluate environmental impacts at a global or regional scale, which makes them poorly suited to detect localised soil degradation. The cost and difficulty of collecting reliable, site-specific soil data also limit the integration of these variables into conventional LCA studies (Galdric, 2014).

These methodological gaps are well illustrated in Table 11, which summarises how key soil-related factors in agricultural systems are (or are not) currently addressed within LCA studies. While water consumption and greenhouse gas emissions are commonly quantified, critical aspects such as soil nutrient depletion, erosion, biodiversity, and changes in organic matter are consistently overlooked. Even the mechanical impacts of agricultural operations (e.g. tillage or harvesting) are only partially captured, focusing on fuel use rather than how such practices alter the soil's physical and biological properties.

Table 11. Factors which are considered of an agricultural process by LCA methodology

Factors to be assessed	CONSIDERED IN LCA?
Assesses the environmental impacts of the production process of a crop	No, it is only considered what inputs are used and which are the outputs. It is not analysed how the process affects to the ecosystem
Water consumption	Yes, considering also the pollution of this resource along all the process.
GHG	Yes, as one of the outputs generated from the system
Mechanical processes (sown, harvested, etc.)	There are some impacts that are considered such as the fuel consumption, the impact from producing the machinery, the energy consumed. However, it is not considered what is happening, and which consequences will occur on the soil.
Depletion of soil nutrients soil nutrients	No
Soil erosion due to ploughing	No
It takes into account the needs of the soil and optimises fertiliser consumption.	No
They take into account the needs for a particular type of crop	No
Evaluation of how the organic matter vary	No
Soil biodiversity	No

Source: Self elaboration

This omission confirms the need to complement conventional LCA with additional indicators and tools that are specifically designed to assess **soil quality, resilience and degradation risks**, thus improving the accuracy, depth, and policy relevance of sustainability assessments in the context of the bioeconomy.

4.4 Filling the Knowledge Gap

Addressing the limitations identified in current LCA methodologies regarding soil assessment requires developing a harmonised and operational approach to integrate soil quality indicators into environmental evaluations, particularly in the context of the bioeconomy. This is a key knowledge gap that SUSTRACK aims to fill.

Literature Screening and Methodological Framing

To explore this gap, an extensive bibliographic analysis was conducted. First, the results of T2.1 served as a foundation, where a bibliographic analysis was conducted. Then, 62 potentially

relevant publications were identified through academic databases such as Google Scholar, ScienceDirect, Scopus, Springer, and ResearchGate. Keywords included "LCA", "soil quality", "land use", "environmental impact", and "bioeconomy".

Publications were filtered based on thematic relevance and publication date. As shown in Figure 6, 57 of the sources were published in the last 20 years, 37 in the last 10 years, and 18 in the last 5 years. After a refined review process, 16 key studies were selected. The final selection includes major contributions by authors such as Vidal Legaz, Fan, van der Werf, Consoli, Beck, de Baan, and Alvarenga, who have developed critical frameworks for soil impact assessment in LCA and land use modelling. Figure 6 shows how the bibliographic analysis process has been developed and the pre-selection done based on the date of publication.

Figure 6. Bibliographic consultation (Source: Self elaboration)

Following this screening, a refined subset of 16 core studies was selected. These included major contributions by authors such as Vidal Legaz, Fan, van der Werf, Consoli, Beck, de Baan, and Alvarenga, who have developed critical frameworks for soil impact assessment in LCA and land use modelling. These sources not only helped identify a relevant pool of candidate indicators but also provided methodological insights to frame the selection process. In particular, they emphasise several core principles for improving soil representation in LCA:

- The importance of considering soil functions, not only land occupation or land use
- The need to include spatially explicit and temporally dynamic indicators
- The distinction between land use impacts and soil degradation processes
- The potential of entropy, exergy, and biological indicators to reflect system-level changes in soil beyond input-output balances

Building on these principles, a multi-criteria selection framework was developed based on the following dimensions:

- **Ease of measurement:** availability of standardised, accessible and replicable methods (field, lab, or model-based).

- **Cost-effectiveness:** feasibility of implementation in operational contexts, including research, monitoring and policy evaluation.
- **Informative value for LCA:** capacity of the indicator to reflect key soil functions and relate to established LCA impact categories (e.g., climate change, resource use, land degradation, biodiversity loss).

Based on these criteria, the following matrix has been developed (Figure 7). The X-axis represents ease of measurement, the Y-axis represents implementation cost, and the size and colour of the dot reflect its informative value for integration into LCA frameworks.

Figure 7. Indicator Prioritisation Matrix (Source: Self elaboration)

Selected Indicators

Based on the screening matrix and literature review, six indicators were selected as most promising for inclusion in LCA methodologies (Table 12).

Detailed Description of Selected Indicators

To support the practical integration of soil quality into Life Cycle Assessment, the six indicators identified as most suitable are described in greater detail below. Each paragraph outlines the specific soil function the indicator represents, the standard method of measurement, and its relevance to LCA categories and applications within the bioeconomy.

Table 12. Selected indicators for inclusion in LCA methodologies

Indicator	Soil function Represented	LCA linkage	Main references
Soil organic carbon	Carbon cycling, fertility, structure	Climate change, long-term productivity	Vidal Legaz, Fan, Beck
Bulk Density	Compaction, porosity, root development	Soil degradation via machinery use	van der Werf, Beck
pH	Chemical balance, microbial activity	Acidification, nutrient availability	Fan, Vidal Legaz
Electrical conductivity	Salinity and nutrient excess	Fertiliser and irrigation-related impacts	Beck, Fan
Earthworm abundance	Soil biodiversity and structure	Proxy for biological activity and resilience	Vidal Legaz, van der Werf
Soil Erosion (RUSLE)	Physical degradation and topsoil loss	Land degradation, sediment loss, productivity	Consoli, Beck, Fan

Source: Self elaboration

Soil Organic Carbon (SOC) is one of the most critical indicators of soil health, reflecting the capacity of the soil to store carbon, support fertility, and regulate water retention and aggregate stability. It serves as a proxy for the balance between organic matter inputs and decomposition, making it highly relevant in agricultural and bio-based systems. SOC is typically measured through laboratory analysis using loss-on-ignition or dry combustion techniques (elemental analysis), both of which are standardised and widely used. In the context of LCA, SOC is particularly valuable as it directly connects to the climate change impact category—soils can either act as carbon sinks or emitters depending on management practices. Furthermore, SOC can be dynamically modelled using tools such as RothC or CENTURY, allowing integration into scenario-based assessments. The high informativeness, combined with increasing policy attention to soil carbon sequestration, makes SOC a cornerstone indicator in sustainable bioeconomy evaluations.

Bulk Density is a physical indicator that reflects the compaction status and porosity of the soil. High bulk density values typically indicate reduced pore space, poor water infiltration, restricted root development, and lower biological activity. The indicator is measured through field sampling using soil cores, which are then oven-dried to determine the mass per unit volume. The procedure is simple, cost-effective, and widely used in both research and applied settings. In relation to LCA, bulk density helps assess the long-term physical degradation of soils due to intensive mechanisation or repeated tillage—factors that are often considered in LCA via fuel or energy inputs but not in terms of their direct effects on soil structure. Including this indicator bridges that gap and enhances the interpretation of land use impacts.

Soil pH is a chemical property essential for nutrient availability, microbial activity, and overall soil fertility. Deviations from optimal pH levels can significantly affect plant uptake of key elements and alter the activity of soil organisms. Measuring soil pH is straightforward, using either field kits or laboratory solutions (commonly water or CaCl₂ extractions). Its low cost and replicability make it suitable for large-scale assessments and monitoring. In LCA, soil pH influences categories such as acidification potential and nutrient efficiency, especially in systems relying heavily on synthetic

inputs. By incorporating soil pH into LCA, practitioners can better evaluate the sustainability of fertilisation strategies and their long-term impact on soil function.

Electrical Conductivity (EC) serves as an indicator of soil salinity and the presence of soluble salts, which can accumulate due to excessive fertiliser application or inefficient irrigation practices. High salinity affects plant growth, microbial processes, and nutrient balance, particularly in arid or intensively irrigated regions. EC is measured using conductivity meters in either soil paste extracts or diluted solutions. The method is rapid, inexpensive, and suitable for field assessments. From an LCA perspective, EC enables a more detailed understanding of water-related impacts, complementing traditional water use metrics by highlighting the degradation of soil quality due to saline accumulation. This is especially relevant in Mediterranean and semi-arid systems where water scarcity and salinisation are closely linked.

Earthworm Abundance is a biological indicator representing soil biodiversity, organic matter turnover, and physical structuring. Earthworms contribute to nutrient cycling, improve soil porosity, and are sensitive to land use practices, particularly those involving tillage, pesticide use, or organic amendments. Earthworm counts are conducted through manual sampling of standardised plots, often complemented by extraction techniques (e.g., mustard solution). While more labour-intensive than other indicators, the method is cost-effective and well-established. In LCA, this indicator provides a critical link to soil biological functioning, an area often overlooked in current impact categories. As a proxy for ecosystem resilience, its inclusion enriches biodiversity assessments and offers a biological counterpart to chemical and physical indicators.

Soil Erosion, commonly estimated through models like the Revised Universal Soil Loss Equation (RUSLE), quantifies the physical loss of topsoil due to water runoff and land mismanagement. Erosion depletes fertile layers, reduces crop yields, and leads to off-site impacts such as sedimentation in water bodies. RUSLE integrates variables such as rainfall intensity, slope, soil type, vegetation cover, and conservation practices. While the model requires spatial data and calibration, it is accessible and widely implemented through GIS platforms. Within LCA, erosion represents a long-term degradation pathway not captured by traditional inventory flows. Its inclusion enables a more comprehensive understanding of land use intensity and sustainability over time, aligning LCA with land degradation neutrality goals and soil conservation policies.

4.5 Integration in SUSTRACK

The preceding analysis has highlighted key methodological limitations of traditional LCA in capturing soil-related impacts. Within SUSTRACK, this task has focused on identifying practical and scientifically grounded ways to address this gap by integrating relevant soil indicators into the LCA framework.

Through a targeted literature review and assessment of existing methodologies, several soil quality indicators were evaluated based on feasibility, cost, and informational value. From an initial broader inventory—including parameters such as land use change, nutrient content, compaction, biological activity, and salinity—a subset of six indicators was prioritised: Soil Organic Carbon, Bulk Density, pH, Electrical Conductivity, Earthworm Abundance, and Soil Erosion (RUSLE).

These indicators offer a balance between operational simplicity and the ability to reflect critical soil functions relevant to bio-based systems. Their inclusion strengthens LCA by capturing degradation pathways and ecosystem services that are often overlooked. Moreover, they provide meaningful insights into long-term land productivity, resilience, and environmental trade-offs.

across value chains. This integration supports SUSTRACK's aim of improving sustainability assessment tools for the circular bioeconomy, aligning with current EU soil and land use strategies.

Figure 8. The next steps to address "the soil gap" (Source: self-elaboration)

5. FINDINGS

D2.3 presents the results of the work carried out in SUSTRACK T2.2. The task focused on the development of new indicators applicable for monitoring and evaluating the transition to circular bio-based systems, which were identified as gaps across the set of indicators that emerged in D2.1. A list of research gaps and recommendations was provided to advance bioeconomy monitoring and evaluation at different policy levels. D2.2 contained the first round of reporting on the development of the three innovative indicator types selected, which has been finalised in D2.3. Now follow summary sections per item on the aim of the research, activities conducted and main findings.

5.1 Knowledge development on Governance indicators

In RP1, the central focus was to develop the most appropriate methodology to build the governance indicator framework. The research was based on a two-step qualitative process involving literature review and stakeholder interviews. Links with other SUSTRACK activities were shared and discussed, such as how this research step should contribute to the monitoring system developed in T2.3 and the case study that is analysed in WP3. This is also the reason why the stakeholders to be involved in this participatory process were gathered from the local context of Prato, Italy (context of one of the case studies). A partial list of companies and organisations to be involved has been mapped.

Throughout RP2, substantial progress was made in translating the conceptual groundwork on governance indicators, initially outlined in D2.2, into concrete outputs informed by real-world application. The work undertaken focused on bridging the gap between theoretical constructs and operational monitoring needs within the framework of CBBE. This required not only clarifying what constitutes governance in this context but also identifying how to measure it meaningfully across different governance scales and sectoral dynamics.

The activities initiated during the second reporting period placed particular emphasis on embedding governance indicators within a multilevel and multi-actor transition logic. Informed by the findings of WP1 and the challenges captured during stakeholder consultations in WP3, was developed and refined a short-list of governance indicators capable of revealing structural conditions that either enable or hinder cooperation, alignment, and institutional learning. These included indicators such as the presence of strategic roadmaps or bioeconomy action plans at the regional level, the establishment of cross-sectoral platforms for stakeholder engagement, the level of transparency in policy implementation, and the degree of inter-institutional coordination between local, national, and EU-level entities. To test the robustness and sectoral relevance of the proposed indicators, mapping and analysing governance indicators across the four SUSTRACK sectors were conducted. In this context, the Prato textile case study was particularly illustrative: it showed how weak coordination mechanisms between local governments and industry associations can hinder the uptake of sustainability-oriented certifications and complicate access to public support mechanisms. This empirical insight reaffirmed the need for indicators that go beyond formal policy existence and instead evaluate the effectiveness, inclusivity, and consistency of governance efforts.

Final findings confirm that governance indicators must be able to reflect both procedural and institutional quality. As a result, the deliverable proposes a dual-level governance indicator framework: one level assessing structural aspects such as the presence of strategy documents or collaborative frameworks, and a second level capturing dynamic processes such as policy adaptability, responsiveness to feedback, and stakeholder co-responsibility. The resulting

framework is not only conceptually grounded but also aligned with the operational needs of the monitoring tool under development in T2.3. This advancement marks a significant step forward in SUSTRACK's capacity to capture governance as a determinant of success in bioeconomy transitions, offering policymakers a more nuanced instrument for identifying barriers and leveraging transformation potential.

5.2 Knowledge development on Externality indicators

This section explores the role of monetised factors, also called the true price gap, and how they can illustrate the distinction between the (*direct*) *market price* of a specific activity and the inherent value for externalities (also called *external costs* or *indirect costs*) caused by that activity to others (like a whole region). Examples of external costs to the planet and people are restoration costs for air and water pollution, compensation costs for labour underpayments. The distinction enables a fairer comparison between total (direct and indirect) costs and benefits from fossil-based activities versus circular bioeconomy-based activities.

The central focus of work in T2.2 was knowledge development about the concept and scope of the topic 'internalisation of externalities' based on desk research and exchanges with sister projects such as FoodCost and SUSTCERT4BIOBASED that also work on the topic. In addition, linkages with other SUSTRACK activities have been acknowledged, like how the monitoring system developed in T2.3 and the case studies analysed in WP3 can benefit from the new indicators set. Instead of quantifying the external costs ourselves, we found some recent studies on external costs valuation due to activities of - at the moment - mainly fossil-based industries, but have the potential to transfer into circular bio-based pathways. These are for chemical, cement, steel and textile production in the EU27.

The calculation of external costs of economic activities is a complex and knowledge-intensive task, as it will depend on the type of industry, production pathway considered, connections within the value chain, geographical location where production takes place and reliance on other regions for materials, land and labour. Though external costs must not be considered as 'the' just one and only values, they, however, provide insight into the type and size of damages brought to the planet and people due to goods produced by the studied industries. In that context, (rough) external costs could be estimated from these examples for the case study activities conducted in WP3 of SUSTRACK.

Last but not least, the gained knowledge on external costs could initiate awareness and better strategic policy decision making about which value chain or industry to support in a specific region, i.e. either to continue with business-as-usual linear production processes or to stimulate circular pathways. Hotspots for intervention are highlighted where best to mitigate external costs resulting from a specific industrial production. Such interventions could, e.g. deal with the adoption of circular and greener textile pathways via promotion of recycling and reuse of textile and plastics materials: promoting recycling and reuse of textiles could reduce external costs by 20-30% according to the Ellen MacArthur Foundation (2017). Moreover, sustainable practices to lower pollution costs can be achieved via the adoption of low-carbon construction materials and technologies to reduce GHG emissions or via implementing stricter wastewater treatment standards and reducing microplastics can significantly lower pollution costs, while the encouragement of organic cotton farming and sustainable materials can mitigate soil degradation and biodiversity loss.

5.3 Knowledge development on LCA-based indicators

The aim of this part is to integrate soil as a limited resource in LCA studies to assess the sustainability of the bioeconomy, ensuring a comprehensive evaluation of the environmental and social impacts of bioeconomic activities. By properly integrating soil into LCA studies, it aims to provide decision-makers and industry stakeholders with a more robust and comprehensive tool to evaluate and improve the sustainability of bioeconomic activities, thus promoting a more equitable and sustainable development of the bioeconomy.

During the first reporting period, the main objective was to define the state of the art regarding the treatment of soil in LCA. A literature review was carried out, alongside the analysis of existing frameworks and case studies from T2.1. This phase highlighted that current LCA methodologies typically address soil only indirectly—via inputs and outputs—without evaluating internal soil processes or long-term degradation. As a result, the need to complement LCA with additional soil indicators was clearly identified.

In the second reporting period, the work focused on identifying which soil quality indicators could be realistically and effectively integrated into LCA frameworks. A refined bibliographic analysis was conducted, based on a curated selection of 16 key references. These were assessed to identify measurable, cost-effective, and informative indicators relevant to soil functions and LCA impact categories. As a result, a set of six indicators was selected: **Soil Organic Carbon**, **Bulk Density**, **pH**, **Electrical Conductivity**, **Earthworm Abundance**, and **Soil Erosion (RUSLE)**. These indicators offer a balanced and practical way to improve the representation of soil in environmental assessments.

The analysis confirms that soil is largely underrepresented in traditional LCA, despite its central role in ecosystem functioning and bioeconomy sustainability. Through the integration of the selected indicators, LCA can better capture soil degradation risks, long-term productivity impacts, and ecosystem service losses. This contribution addresses a key methodological gap and supports more holistic and harmonised sustainability assessments within the SUSTRACK framework.

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